

**“COMPARISON OF THE DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF
SONOMAMMOGRAPHY WITH HISTOPATHOLOGY IN
THE EVALUATION OF BREAST MASSES”**

BY

DR. GUTTA GOUTHAM KRISHNA

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IN

RADIO-DIAGNOSIS

UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF

DR. SHIVANAND V. PATIL

PROFESSOR,

DEPARTMENT OF RADIODIAGNOSIS

DR. VIJAYALAXMI PATIL

ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR,

DEPARTMENT OF PATHOLOGY

B.L.D.E (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY), SHRI B M PATIL

MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE,

VIJAYAPURA, KARNATAKA

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RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

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Date:

Place: Vijayapura

DR. GUTTA GOUTHAM KRISHNA
Post Graduate Student,
Department of Radiodiagnosis,
B.L.D.E.U’ s Shri B. M. Patil Medical
College, Hospital & Research Centre,
Vijayapura.

B.L.D.E. UNIVERSITY'S
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

CERTIFICATE BY THE GUIDE

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Date:

Place: Vijayapura

DR. SHIVANAND V. PATIL
Professor,
Department of Radiodiagnosis,
B.L.D.E.U' s Shri B. M. Patil Medical College,
Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura.

DR. VIJAYALAXMI PATIL
Associate Professor,
Department of Pathology,
B.L.D.E.U' s Shri B. M. Patil Medical College,
Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura.

B.L.D.E. UNIVERSITY'S
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

ENDORSEMENT BY THE HEAD OF DEPARTMENT

This to certify that the dissertation entitled “**COMPARISON OF THE DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF SONOMAMMOGRAPHY WITH HISTOPATHOLOGY IN THE EVALUATION OF BREAST MASSES**” is a bonafide research work done by **DR. GUTTA GOUTHAM KRISHNA** under the guidance of **DR. SHIVANAND V. PATIL**, Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis and **DR. VIJAYALAXMI PATIL**, Associate Professor, Department of Pathology at B.L.D.E.U’ s Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura

DR. RAJASHEKHAR MUCHCHANDI
Professor and HOD
Department of Radiodiagnosis,
B.L.D.E.U’ s Shri B. M. Patil Medical College,
Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura.

B.L.D.E. UNIVERSITY'S
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

ENDORSEMENT BY THE PRINCIPAL

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Date:

Place: Vijayapura

DR. ARAVIND PATIL
Principal,
B.L.D.E.U' s
Shri B. M. Patil Medical College,
Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura.

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Date:

Place: Vijayapura

DR. GUTTA GOUTHAM KRISHNA

Post Graduate Student,
Department of Radiodiagnosis,
B.L.D.E.U' s Shri B. M. Patil Medical
College, Hospital & Research Centre,
Vijayapura.

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Date:

Place: Vijayapura.

Dr. Gutta Goutham Krishna

ABSTRACT

COMPARISON OF THE DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF SONOMAMMOGRAPHY WITH HISTOPATHOLOGY IN THE EVALUATION OF BREAST MASSES

BACKGROUND

The most well-known methods for breast cancer screening and diagnosis are mammography and ultrasound. This study assessed the diagnostic accuracy of sonomammography for benign and malignant breast lesions independently, as well as the reliability of the results when verified by histopathology.

METHODS

Patients eligible for the study were received and counseled about the study. After obtaining informed written consent, history was taken, and the patient underwent a brief clinical examination. Following this, they were subjected to an extensive Sonomammography (SMG) interrogation of the mass. The patient further underwent a comprehensive Histopathological Examination of the mass, and the Sonomammographic and Histopathological findings so obtained were compared with each other by Statistical Analysis for calculation of the sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values of SMG and comparison of SMG with that of Histopathology.

RESULTS

100 patients were selected for analysis, presenting with 118 masses. Out of them, 36 patients had malignancy, and 82 were benign. USG successfully differentiated between benign and malignant masses when the BI-RADS lexicon was incorporated with a sensitivity of 100% and a specificity of 97.56% for malignant masses.

INTERPRETATION AND CONCLUSION

USG can be used as a good screening test for the detection and differentiation of benign and malignant masses. Hence, it helps in early detection, early treatment and favorable outcome.

KEYWORDS

Breast, USG

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

SMG	-	Sonomammography
MMG	-	Mammography
USG	-	Ultrasonography
HPR	-	Histopathology Report
CT	-	Computed Tomography
HU	-	Hounsfield Unit
MRI	-	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NPV	-	Negative Predictive Value
PPV	-	Positive Predictive Value
Sen	-	Sensitivity
Spe	-	Specificity
BC	-	Breast Cancer

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INTRODUCTION

Around a quarter (25%) of all cancer cases in women are breast cancer, making it the most frequent cancer in the world for women. Prior until recently, cervical cancer was the most frequent cancer among Indian women; however, the primary cause of cancer-related mortality is breast cancer, which is currently more common than cervical cancer. In rural India, cervical cancer is still more prevalent.^{1,2} Breast cancer (BC) death and incidence rates adjusted for age are approximately 12.7 and 25.8 per 100,000 persons in India, respectively.² Right now, mortality rates are falling despite of rising incidence. Screening, early discovery, and better treatment may have impacted the decline.³

The majority of female patients, in the imaging department, have a breast deformity that can be felt. The appropriate order and degree of imaging that are needed are still unclear.⁴ Breast lumps have a relatively good predictive value for malignancy and are the most prevalent presenting symptom among women with breast cancer.⁴ Non-lump breast abnormalities such nipple retractions (7%) and breast discomfort (6%) as well as non-breast symptoms like back pain (1%) and weight loss (0.3%) are other less prevalent observations.⁵

Figure 1:

Breast Symptomatology

Even with more aggressive treatment, the prognosis is not as excellent as in previous stages when over 50% of women with breast cancer arrive in stages 3 and 4. Diseases may present later than expected for a variety of reasons, including ignorance, financial hardship, or lack of

awareness. Early detection and diagnosis of BC are essential since they lower the province's death rate and raise the likelihood that patients will benefit from thorough medical care.⁶

Beginning in the middle of the 1990s, developments in imaging technology fundamentally altered how women with detectable breast tumors were assessed. With the development of high-megahertz linear array transducers with improved near-field resolution, compound imaging, and harmonics, ultrasound technology applied to breast imaging significantly improved, resulting in improved characterization of the shape, margins, and internal echotexture of masses.⁷

Mammography is necessary for women who have breast masses or lesions, but occasionally, especially in young women, heavy breast tissue limits the sensitivity of the scan. A suitable diagnostic method for identifying breast cancer under these circumstances is ultrasonic mammography. In addition to determining a breast's palpable mass, breast ultrasonography, also known as sonomammography, can remove cysts from solid masses and identify abnormalities in the peripheral view that mammography will miss.⁸

The breast-imaging reporting and data system (BI-RADS) lexicon was created by the American College of Radiography as a common nomenclature to compile the results of several breast-imaging procedures, including MRI, USG, and MMG.⁹ In our investigation, we also used the BI-RADS lexicon.

In many instances, histopathological analysis is still the primary means of distinguishing benign from malignant lesions.¹⁰

Therefore, the purpose of the current study was to evaluate the performance of sonomammography in distinguishing between benign and malignant breast cancers and to confirm the findings through histology. An attempt was made to diagnose and categorize the lesions using BI-RADS terminology in ultrasonography.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To have a thorough understanding of the breast architecture, anatomical variations and pathologies to attain an optimal diagnostic approach.
2. To have a clear understanding of the disease's specific location and scope, which is crucial for management decisions.
3. To appropriately diagnose and stage any breast mass, including its site and any expansions that have migrated to neighboring structures.
4. To correlate SMG diagnosis with histopathological findings.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

EMBRYOLOGY OF THE BREAST [11-17]

The development of the mammary gland, also known as the breast, starts about the fifth week of fetal development and is a modified form of the apocrine sweat gland. Various systemic and local growth agents and hormones regulate this series of intricately arranged events. The paired linear ectodermal ridges, also known as mammary ridges,^{13,14} are thicker ectoderm strips that extend bilaterally on the embryo's ventral surface from the axillary to the inguinal regions. These ridges are the source of the breast. In human embryos, these buds die during the seventh week of pregnancy, leaving only one pair of solid buds—the primary mammary buds—that remain at the fourth or fifth intercostal gap. The development of ectopic breast tissue (polymastia) and/or supernumerary nipples (polythelia) along the mammary ridge is caused by incomplete involution of the linear ectodermal ridge, and it can occur in 1-6 percent of people.¹⁵ Once these initial ectoderm buds pierce down into the underlying mesoderm, the breasts start to form. The primary mammary buds develop into secondary buds around the 12th week of pregnancy, which ultimately results in the formation of the mammary lobules. The mammary ridge pierces the underlying mesoderm in the fifth month of pregnancy, radially extending 15–20 branching ingrowths into the developing breast.¹³ The lactiferous ducts and their branches are formed by tiny lumina that originate inside the mammary buds. During infancy, the shallow breast pit that the lactiferous ducts converge into becomes a nipple. Sweat glands, sebaceous glands, and apocrine glands continue to form during the second trimester of pregnancy, culminating in the production of the Montgomery glands. Additionally, the areola begins to grow at around 5 months of gestation. The primary lactiferous ducts form identical breasts in boys and females at birth. The nipple emerges from the areola shortly after birth,¹² encircling 10–15 terminal duct openings.

Normal Breast Development

The primary lactiferous ducts, which carry colostrum, allow the 15–20 radially organized mammary lobes that make up the breast to drain into ampullae upon birth. Newborns produce colostrum between postpartum days 4 and 7, which is triggered by placental hormones. Consequently, it is usual for any sex at this age to have a milky nipple discharge. Additional branching and terminal lobule development occur during the first two years of life. Breast development is halted between the ages of two and thelarche. The hypothalamus pituitary gonadal axis and the hypothalamic pituitary adrenal axis, respectively, control the biology of pubic hair production and breast development.¹⁶ In North American girls, the onset of puberty typically coincides with the ages between 8 and 12, coinciding with the growing secretion of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) by the hypothalamus. (The typical age range for puberty varies by region, race, and ethnicity). The pituitary gland secretes luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) in response to gonadal reticulum (GnRH), which induces the maturation of ovarian follicles and their production of progestins

and estrogen. Ovarian estrogen causes the surrounding stroma and mammary ductal epithelium to proliferate, which in turn causes the terminal duct lobular units, collecting ducts, and breast buds to proliferate.¹⁵ As the volume of the breast grows, vascular and connective tissue components multiply together. Tanner (1976) published a description of the most widely used method for adolescent breast and pubic hair development staging (Table 1).¹⁷

Table 1: Tanner’s Breast Developmental Stages

Stages	Development
I (Preadolescent)	Elevation of the papilla above the chest wall's level.
II (Breast budding)	Elevation of the breast and papillae, as well as a larger areola diameter.
III	Persistent areolar and breast hypertrophy.
IV:	The papilla and areola elevate over the breast mound.
V (Mature breast):	Elevation of the papilla and areolar regression.

ANATOMY OF THE BREAST AND NIPPLE – AREOLAR COMPLEX [11-15]

The female breast lies superiorly between the second intercostal space and the inframammary fold at the sixth or seventh intercostal space inferiorly on the anterior chest wall. From the lateral boundary of the sternum to the midaxillary line laterally, the breast extends medially along its transverse axis.¹⁴

The pectoralis major muscular fascia makes up about two-thirds of the deep surface of the breast, with the serratus anterior muscle and the top parts of the rectus abdominis and external oblique muscles covered by the bottom lateral thirds. Towards the axilla, Spence's axillary tail expands laterally. Individual differences are noticeable in breast tissue's volume, density, form, and contour.

The breast can be divided into upper inner, upper outer, lower inner, and lower outer quadrants.

More significant amounts of fibroglandular tissue are typically found in the breast's upper outer quadrant than in the remaining area. Moreover, breast cancers most commonly occur there. Breast tissue consists of fibroglandular breast tissue, adipose tissue, and skin. There are hair follicles, sebaceous glands, and eccrine sweat glands under the typically thin skin of the breasts. Adjacent to the skin is the subcutaneous layer. Substratum fascia is found in the fibroglandular breast tissue and beneath this layer. Preceding the muscular fascia of the pectoralis major is the deep fascia. The retro mammary bursa or space, primarily made up of loose areolar tissue and permits breast motion on the chest wall, separates these two structures.

Fibrous bands of connective tissue (Cooper's suspensory ligaments) travel through the breast, connecting the superficial and deep fascia and inserting perpendicularly into the dermis. The breast parenchyma, also known as fibroglandular tissue, is made up of 15-20 lobes that are further subdivided into 20-40 lobules, each of which has 10-100 alveoli.

Minor interlobular ducts are found in each breast lobe, and they empty into major lactiferous ducts, which enlarge to form subareolar lactiferous ampullae. At the nipple, ten large collecting milk ducts open (Fig. 2).

The nipple in a breast free of ptosis is situated at the level of the fourth intercostal gap. During puberty, there is a substantial deposit of basal melanin in the nipple-areolar complex, which darkens. The nipple has a variety of sensory nerve endings, including thermostats and mechanoreceptors called Ruffini corpuscles and Krause end bulbs. Sebaceous glands and apocrine sweat glands are found in the areola. The Morgagni tubercles, nodular elevations created by the Montgomery gland apertures, are dispersed across the areola's perimeter.^{12,15} Nipple erection in response to stimulation is caused by smooth muscle fibers that are radially

organized and reach into the nipple's dermis.

Figure 2

Female Breast.

Vascular Supply[11]

Three sources provide the majority of the blood supply to the breast: (i) branches of the lateral thoracic artery, which supply 30% of the vascular supply to the breast; (ii) medially located internal mammary perforators, which account for 60% of the blood supply to the breast; and (iii) minor contributions from the thoracoacromial, intercostals, subscapular, and thoracodorsal arteries.^{14,15} Rich subdermal plexus supplies the breast skin and communicates with the deeper veins supplying the breast parenchyma. Following the path of the arteries, the breast's venous drainage flows toward the axilla. A portion of the venous drainage also passes through the subcutaneous tissue beneath the nipple-areolar complex, to the circulus venosus, an anastomotic circle.

Figure 3

Arterial supply of the breast.

Figure 4

Pathways of venous drainage of the breast.

Neural Innervation [11]

Anterior and lateral cutaneous branches of the third through sixth intercostal nerves provide the anterolateral chest wall and the breast's sensory innervation—these branches course between slips of the serratus anterior muscle. The skin of the top part of the breast is supplied by cutaneous branches emerging from the anterior branches of the supraclavicular nerve. The lateral cutaneous branch stemming from the second intercostal nerve, the intercostobrachial nerve, supplies sensation over the upper arm's medial aspect, which is encountered during axillary dissection.

Figure 5

Major nerves of the breast and axilla.

Lymphatic Drainage [11]

Over 75% of the breast's lymphatic outflow is made up of twenty to thirty axillary lymph nodes. Through the internal mammary lymph nodes, the medial portion of the breast provides the source of the remaining lymphatic drainage. Surgeons are aware of six axillary lymph node groupings, each with three levels. The scapular group, the external mammary group, and the axillary vein group are level I lymph nodes that are situated lateral to the P. minor muscle. The central group and interpectoral group, also known as Rotter's nodes, are level II lymph nodes that are situated both superficially and deeply to the pectoralis minor muscle. The subclavicular group is among the level III lymph nodes, which are situated medial to the pectoralis minor muscle.

Figures 6 and 7

Lymphatic drainage pathways of the breast.

HISTORY OF SONOGRAPHY IN BREAST IMAGING [18-62]:

Breast sonography has been used for 53 years in clinical and in vitro settings. Differentiating benign from malignant tumors has been explored using a variety of imaging techniques after years of unsuccessful attempts, which at first made it little more than a curiosity. Subsequent advancements in breast ultrasonography gave rise to theorized “automated” devices that may potentially replace X-ray mammography as a screening technique by scanning the entire breast tissue. We have now entirely circled back to breast ultrasonography as the most common guidance system for preoperative localization and percutaneous breast biopsy and as the most significant supplementary breast imaging modality now accessible. Understanding the past of this invaluable breast-imaging technique is crucial to comprehending the considerable role it currently plays.

In 1951, two breast tumors—one benign and the other malignant—in the intact, in vivo breast were reported by Wild and Neal¹⁹ for their acoustic properties. They reported three distinct acoustic signatures based on the observed acoustic impedance for normal breast tissue, benign tumors, and malignant tumors using an elementary high-frequency (15-MHz) device that produced an A-mode sonogram. The results of 21 breast tumor ultrasonography exams—9 benign and 12 malignant—were published by Wild and Reid²⁰ in 1952. The first 2-dimensional breast tissue echograms, or B-mode sonograms, were reported in two cases.

The following year, Howry et al.²¹ used a lower-frequency pulse echo scanner with internal focusing components to decrease beam width and publish two-dimensional pictures of in vitro breast cancers. Both of these adjustments produced better diagnostic-quality images.

In 1954, Wild and Reid published a report on the first clinical use of breast ultrasonography.²² Early studies on sonographic breast imaging did not take into account the possibility of using this modality for screening. It was the exact reverse. The inquiry was not designed to find malignancies, nor was it necessarily meant to take the place of current techniques for diagnosing breast diseases, according to Wild and Reid.²⁰ Nonetheless, it was evident that the main objective was to differentiate between benign and malignant breast tumors, and the outcomes in this respect were highly accurate. Preoperative characterizations of 9 out of 9 benign tumors and 12 out of 12 malignant tumors (11 ductal carcinomas and 1 sarcoma) were accurately performed by Wild and Reid.²⁰

DeLand²³ scanned a total of 19 breast cancers, 16 ductal and 3 medullary, for publication in a 1969 article. Among the equipment modifications he had made were one B-mode system operating at 2.5 MHz and featuring five crystals—one broadcasting and four receiving. Although the emitting crystal lacked focus, some control over the lateral resolution might be obtained by applying a collimator to its face. DeLand also employed a single-breast, supine water path technique, which prevented any modification of the skin's contour. His findings accurately identified 15 of the 16 ductal carcinomas preoperatively, which is a rather precise characterization of the tumors. Nevertheless, none of the three medullary carcinomas were discovered. We now know that the mistake was caused by the fact that medullary carcinoma,

a highly cellular, homogenous kind of tumor, typically shows through-transmission rather than shadowing.

In 1976, a characterization problem arose once more with the study of 18 breast tissue samples by Calderon et al.²⁴: 2 were normal, 7 were benign, and 9 were cancerous. Only one medullary carcinoma was mischaracterized out of the nine carcinomas, with eight of them having accurate descriptions.

Figure 8

Dr. Wild's clinical B-mode instrument.

Figure 9

Dr. Wild scanning a patient's breast using the second iteration of the B-mode scanner he and Reid invented.

DEVELOPMENT AROUND THE WORLD

In the 1960s, the United States, Japan, and Australia were the primary hubs for ongoing breast ultrasonography research. The Royal North Shore Hospital in Sydney erected the nation's first ultrasonic breast scanner in 1966. It was a bistable device with sector, compound, and linear scanning modes for imaging. When gray-scale imaging was introduced in 1969, things vastly improved. In addition to including a focused array format and a gray-scale approach, Kossoff, Jellins, and their colleagues at Commonwealth Acoustic Laboratories also established the principles of gray-scale sonography for all soft tissues..²⁵⁻²⁸

In the United States, Kelly-Fry et al.²⁹⁻³⁰ developed an online computer-controlled system in the late 1960s, which signaled a change in emphasis from tissue characterisation of identified masses to the early identification of subclinical breast diseases. She and her colleagues were the first to analyze the breasts in women of various ages who did not exhibit any symptoms. By examining the echogenic patterns produced by patients in three distinct age groups, they could distinguish between the different structural components of the mammary gland. This was the first attempt to use sonographic techniques to investigate asymptomatic, healthy women, and it is regarded as a pioneering effort in the association of sonographic patterns with breast histopathologic findings.³¹ Kelly-Fry and Kossoff's research revealed marginal variations in ultrasonography velocity in the breasts of patients with varying ages and pathologic conditions.³²

This was confirmed in 1976 by Calderon and colleagues when they discovered that different pathologic states had different acoustic attenuation values, with malignant lesions showing the highest attenuation values. The experiments were done in vitro.²⁴

In the 1960s, Wells and his colleagues in England created a device that used a prone scanning technique with the patient's breast suspended in a water bath with temperature control. The gadget was special at the time.³³ Though, to their credit, only one published study resulted from it; nonetheless, their design found application in the Octoson scanner, developed by Kossoff and Jellins in Australia, and in automated scanners developed by developed by Life Imaging Corporation³⁴⁻³⁷ and Johnson & Johnson (New Brunswick, NJ) (later acquired by Technicare Corporation, Australia).³⁸⁻⁴⁰ These were all created and released in the latter part of the 1970s. A commercial device that used water coupling and required the patient to lie supine on an examination table was marketed by Labsonics (Australia) in the 1980s. Kelly-Fry's continued work in Indiana made this device viable.

The Canadian team led by Foster and Hunt⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ and the Indiana-based Kelly Fry group made transducer design and beam characteristics their top priority.^{29-30,45-47} It was demonstrated by both groups that resolution was not only based on frequency. By tightly controlling the lateral resolution, transducer diameter, and focal length, higher levels of resolution might be attained without altering the frequency. In Japan, a significant amount of ultrasonic research was conducted in the 1950s and 1960s, and Kikuchi et al.'s work showed an interest in breast cancer diagnosis.⁴⁸ They were additionally joined by J. Takada, H. Ito, H. Yokoi, K. Takahashi, S. Hayashi, and T. Kobayashi in a later period.

The majority of research that was published in the early 1970s on the ultrasonic features of benign vs malignant breast disease originated in Japan. The topic was covered in articles by Kasumi et al.⁴⁹ and Kobayashi et al.,⁵⁰⁻⁵³ who evaluated and analyzed roughly 23 distinct diagnostic criteria for the potential separation of benign from malignant breast cancers. The acoustic shadowing feature in these papers came to be associated with malignancy; this idea was subsequently much more rigorously worked out. The Japanese literature placed a strong emphasis on the examination of the supine patient utilizing a single focused transducer and a water bag as a coupling agent. By using transducers with a frequency of roughly 5 MHz higher than previously utilized, the breast examination was conducted with a resolution of about 2 mm.⁵² Around this same period, Japanese researchers created color display systems and started routinely using breast ultrasonography in clinical settings.^{49,50,53}

The Digital Age and Technological Revolution

Digital technology was introduced to the area of ultrasound in general and breast ultrasonography in particular in the early 1980s. Having a digital signal instead of an analog one allowed for many instantaneous resolution gains based on both beam shaping and signal processing. Later, in the early 1990s, advances like tissue harmonics and real-time spatial compounding were made possible by digital beam formers and broad bandwidth capabilities.

Tissue Harmonic Imaging and Spatial Compounding

Tissue harmonic scanning and spatial compounding are the primary advantages of technology for breast imaging. Each stood for the two extremities of the signal processing bell curve. To counteract the many scattering artifacts of ultrasound, tissue harmonic scanning was developed. This narrows the main beam and reduces side lobes, resulting in an image with less noise.⁵⁴ It was first created as an alternative sonographic imaging technique to help identify blood flow more accurately when intravenous sonographic contrast chemicals were first tested in experiments.⁵⁵ In contrast, spatial compounding creates an image that appears smoother by using several beams from multiple angles.⁵⁶ The “open shutter technique,” which involved using a Polaroid camera with an open lens to make multiple arc-like sweeps over the patient’s skin with the transducer, is still remembered by those who scanned in the early 1970s when clinical ultrasound was still being developed. By leveraging digital imaging capabilities, a grayscale image was produced, successfully utilizing the same mechanical principle that is produced electronically by spatial compounding.

Development of Doppler Technology

Theoretically, use of Doppler sonography in the examination of breast masses offered a way to record the existence or non-existence of cancer neovascularity. Early studies of the breast utilizing Doppler sonography were conducted by Jellins and Kossoff in Australia and Burns and Wells in England. Continuous wave Doppler sonography was used to obtain a sensitivity of 95% for cancers and 85% for benign lesions in a series of 70 patients (23 of whom had malignancies), as reported by Jellins et al. in 1983.⁵⁷ Burns, Holliwell, and Wells in England came to the conclusion that the significant Doppler signals found in breast cancers most likely originated from the veins around the tumor rather than necessarily inside of it. In their

investigations, the best way to distinguish between benign and malignant conditions was to compare the peak systolic frequencies of each. Finally, they came to the conclusion that the "multiple feed artery" model was the most likely explanation for the blood flow pattern in the area of breast cancers. The addition of color Doppler to grayscale imaging signalled a significant advancement in Doppler sonography by allowing for even more improvements in the interpretation of the fundamental Doppler data. Even while color Doppler and Power color Doppler investigation of the blood supply to breast tumors has lately increased the specificity of clinical breast ultrasonography, it still falls short of the goal of 100% specificity in separating benign from malignant entities.^{58,59}

The Clinical Revolution

The 1990s saw a significant increase in the clinical use of breast ultrasonography, despite early research publications concentrating on the straightforward distinction between a cyst and a solid. Fornage et al. (1987) evaluated the accuracy of preoperative breast cancer size determination using sonography, clinical examination, and mammography in comparison to mammography.⁶⁰ They demonstrated that the sonographic measurement had the lowest residual standard deviation and the highest correlation coefficient.⁶⁰ This also demonstrated how ultrasound can be used to gauge how a tumor responds to neoadjuvant treatment. As handheld, real-time breast sonography became more accessible, it emerged as the most popular technique for providing guidance during breast tissue fine-needle aspiration and core biopsy procedures. Breast sonography swiftly established itself as the go-to technique for needle biopsy guidance due to its affordability, convenience of use, and real-time capabilities. Fornage et al.⁶¹ published one of the first papers in 1990 detailing the outcomes of USG guided biopsies in 49 breast carcinomas with sizes smaller than 1 cm³, demonstrating the potential of ultrasound to precisely guide the sample of small lesions.

Benign Versus Malignant: The Goal of Lesion Characterization

One of the primary purposes of breast ultrasonography, from the field's founding publications in the early 1950s, has been to try and differentiate benign from malignant tumors using a range of sonographic parameters. In 1995, Stavros published a work on tissue characterization of these parameters.⁶² Based on extensive data obtained from the examination of 750 breast masses, the acoustic properties belonging to both benign and malignant lesions were listed and thoroughly explained. This paper reduced the "gray areas" in interpretation, even if histology examinations are still the gold standard for determining benign from malignant lesions.

Lexicon

A lexicon for reporting results from breast ultrasounds was created that perfectly matched the terminology used in x-ray mammography for a number of years, while simultaneously attuning to the impact of this expanded role of breast ultrasound and underscoring its integral role in evaluating clinical breast problems. This will give clinicians a single manner to communicate all breast imaging results that clearly indicates the suggested clinical care and highlights the overall impression of the scan

ACR BIRADS [63]

ACR BI-RADS is a quality assurance tool that aims to simplify reporting, lessen ambiguity in management recommendations and interpretations of breast imaging, and make outcome tracking easier. The advantages and restrictions of breast imaging technologies should be known to all interpreting doctors and referring healthcare professionals.

Table 2: ACR USG BIRADS Lexicon

Breast Tissue	Terms
A. Tissue composition (screening only)	1. a. Homogeneous background echotexture – fat 2. b. Homogeneous background echotexture – fibroglandular 3. c. Heterogeneous background echotexture
Findings	Terms
B. Masses	1. Shape a. Oval b. Round c. Irregular
	2. Orientation a. Parallel b. Not parallel
	3. Margin a. Circumscribed b. Not circumscribed i. Indistinct ii. Angular iii. Microlobulated iv. Spiculated
	4. Echo pattern a. Anechoic b. Hyperechoic c. Complex cystic and solid d. Hypoechoic e. Isoechoic f. Heterogeneous
	5. Posterior features a. No posterior features b. Enhancement c. Shadowing d. Combined pattern
C. Calcifications	1. Calcifications in a mass 2. Calcifications outside of a mass 3. Intraductal calcifications
D. Associated features	1. Architectural distortion
	2. Duct changes
	3. Skin changes a. Skin thickening b. Skin retraction
	4. Edema
	5. Vascularity a. Absent b. Internal vascularity c. Vessels in rim
	6. Elasticity assessment a. Soft b. Intermediate c. Hard
E. Special cases	1. Simple cyst
	2. Clustered microcysts
	3. Complicated cyst
	4. Mass in or on skin
	5. Foreign body including implants
	6. Lymph nodes – intramammary
	7. Lymph nodes – axillary
	8. Vascular abnormalities a. AVMs (arteriovenous malformations/pseudoaneurysms) b. Mondor disease
	9. Postsurgical fluid collection
	10. Fat necrosis

A. BREAST TISSUE COMPOSITION

USG pictures exhibit the same broad normal range in tissue composition as mammography. Heterogeneous background echotexture of the breast may impact the sensitivity of breast sonograms for lesion detection, in the same way as increasing breast density reduces the sensitivity of mammography in the detection of tiny masses.

a. Homogeneous Echotexture — Fat

The majority of breast tissue is composed of consistently echogenic bands of supporting structures and fat lobules.

Figure 10

Homogenous – Fat Echotexture

b. Homogeneous Echotexture — Fibroglandular

Beneath the thin hypoechoic layer of fat lobules is a thick zone of homogeneously echogenic fibroglandular parenchyma. Numerous diseases, tumors, and fibroadenomas, for example, are located in the fibroglandular zone or where it meets the adipose layer.

Figure 11
Homogenous – Fibroglandular Echotexture

c. Heterogeneous Echotexture

There are two types of heterogeneity: focused and diffuse. Multiple tiny regions of increased and decreased echogenicity define the breast echotexture. Shadowing can happen where the parenchyma and fat lobules meet. Younger breasts and those with heterogeneously thick parenchyma as shown on mammograms have this pattern.

Figure 12
Heterogenous Echotexture

B. MASSES

A mass is spatial and three-dimensional. It should be visible in two distinct planes when using 2-D US; three planes when using volumetric acquisitions. Using two or more projections and real-time scanning, masses can be differentiated from typical anatomic structures, such as ribs or fat.

1. Shape

a. Oval

An elliptical or egg-shaped mass (possibly with two or three undulations, such as macrolobulations or gentle lobulations).

Figure 13
Oval Shaped Mass

b. Round

A round mass might be globular, round, spherical, or ball-shaped. Its transverse diameter is the same as its anteroposterior diameter; it must be circular in perpendicular projections to qualify as a round mass. Masses with a round shape are not commonly seen on breast US.

Figure 14
Round Shaped Mass

c. Irregular

The lesion shape is neither round nor oval.

Figure 15
Irregular Shaped Mass

2. Orientation

Only USG imaging possesses this mass characteristic. Orientation is defined in reference to the skin line. The classification of masses positioned obliquely as parallel or non-parallel can be aided by the observation of their long axes, which may exhibit a radial pattern. Most benign masses, especially fibroadenomas, have a parallel or "wider-than-tall" orientation; yet, many carcinomas also have this orientation. The only characteristic that should be considered for determining if a mass is malignant should not be its orientation.

a. Parallel (historically, "wider-than-tall" or "horizontal")

The mass's long axis runs parallel to the skin's surface. Only somewhat obliquely oriented masses could be regarded as parallel.

Figure 16
Parallel Orientation

b. Not Parallel

The long axis of the bulk is not parallel to the surface of the skin. Compared to the anterior-posterior or vertical dimension, the transverse or horizontal dimension is smaller. These aggregates can also be oriented obliquely in the direction of the skin's surface. The orientation of round masses is not parallel.

Figure 17
Not Parallel Orientation

3. Margin

The lesion's border or edge is known as the margin. The descriptors of margin, like shape descriptors, are significant predictors of whether a mass is benign or malignant.

a. Circumscribed (“well-defined” or “sharply defined”)

A well-defined border that abruptly breaks the surrounding tissue is known as a circumscribed margin. In the US, a mass needs to have a well-defined margin throughout in order to be considered confined. Most circumscribed lesions have an oval or round shape.

Figure 18
Circumscribed

b. Not Circumscribed

If any part of the margin is not circumscribed, the mass has to be classified as non-circumscribed. In addition, a mass that is not delimited can be defined as having angular, spiculated, microlobulated, or unclear borders. It is not used to aggregate these marginal features because irregular depicts the form of a mass.

i. Indistinct

The entire margin or any part of the margin is not clearly separated from the surrounding tissue. The mass is not confined, which is a major trait despite the poorly defined boundaries. Since it might be difficult to tell the difference between a margin that is indistinct and one that exhibits an echogenic rim, the term "indistinct" also refers to echogenic rim (formerly known as "echogenic halo").

Figure 19
Indistinct Margin

ii. Angular

The margin of the mass is not delimited, which is an important trait. Part of the margin has sharp corners, which often form acute angles.

Figure 20
Angular Margin

iii. Microlobulated

Short-cycle undulations describe the margin, but the most important aspect is that the mass's margin is unconstrained.

Figure 21
Microlobulated Margin

iv. Spiculated

Sharp lines emanating from the mass, which are frequently indicative of cancer, define the margin; nonetheless, the most important characteristic is that the mass's margin is unbounded.

Figure 22
Spiculated Margin

4. Echopattern

When compared to mammary fat, the majority of benign and malignant tumors have hypoechoic echogenicity. Even though many fully echogenic masses are benign, it is more trustworthy to make a prospective benign evaluation based on margin descriptions. While the

echo pattern along with other feature categories aids in the evaluation of a breast lesion, echogenicity on its own is not very specific.

a. Anechoic

No evidence of any internal echoes.

Figure 23
Anechoic Echopattern

b. Hyperechoic

Being more echogenic than fat or having echogenicity comparable to fibroglandular tissue is known as hyperechogenicity.

Figure 24
Hyperechoic Echopattern

c. Complex Cystic and Solid

Both anechoic (cystic or fluid) and echogenic (solid) components can be found in a complex mass.

Figure 25

Complex Cystic and Solid Echopattern

d. Hypoechoic

The term "hypoechoic" is in regard to subcutaneous fat; hypoechoic tumors (complex cysts and fibroadenomas) are less echogenic than fat and have low-level echoes throughout.

Figure 26

Hypoechoic Echopattern

e. Isoechoic

To be isoechogenic means to be echogenic, similar to subcutaneous fat. If an isoechoic mass is located within a region of fat lobules, it may be somewhat undetectable. This could reduce USG sensitivity, particularly during screening when the existence and location of such a mass are unknown at the time of the exam.

Figure 27
Isoechoic Echopattern

f. Heterogeneous

Heterogeneity, a combination of echogenic patterns within a solid mass, is frequently seen in both malignancies and fibroadenomas. Heterogeneity is not very useful in predicting the prognosis of benign from malignant masses. Particularly in a mass with non-circumscribed boundaries and an uneven shape, clumped patches with varying echogenicity may raise the suspicion of malignancy.

Figure 28
Heterogeneous Echopattern

5. Posterior Features

The attenuation properties of a mass with regard to its acoustic transmission are represented by its posterior aspects. Additional characteristics of masses include enhancement and attenuation (shadowing), which are primarily of secondary rather than main prognostic relevance.

a. No Posterior Features

Deep beneath the mass, there is neither shadowing nor augmentation; the region immediately behind the bulk has the same echogenicity as the surrounding tissue at the same depth.

Figure 29

No Posterior Acoustic Features

b. Enhancement

There is no obstruction to sound transmission across the bulk. A column of enhanced material appears deeper in the bulk and is more echogenic, or whiter. Enhancement is one of the criteria used to diagnose cysts. Elevation may also be seen in homogeneous solid lesions, such as high-grade carcinomas.

Figure 30

Posterior Acoustic Enhancement

c. Shadowing

Attenuation of the acoustic transmission is known as shadowing. The region posterior to the bulk appears darker on sonography. Acoustic velocity varies and thin shadows appear at the edges of bent masses. It is important to separate this refractive edge shadowing from center shadowing, which is a mass feature, as the former is unimportant. Fibrosis is linked to shadowing, whether or not there is an underlying malignancy. Posterior shadowing is seen in fibrous mastopathy, postsurgical scars,

and many malignancies, whether or not there is a desmoplastic response. Macrocalcifications can also reduce sound intensity. Shadowing is a feature that is more beneficial when present than when absent, much like a vertical (taller than wide) orientation. Many tumors, especially high grade ones, will show improvement in their posterior features or show no change at all.

Figure 31

Posterior Acoustic Shadowing

d. Combined Pattern

Multiple patterns of posterior attenuation are present in certain lesions. For instance, shadowing posterior to the calcified part and augmentation of the tissues deep to the uncalcified portion may be seen in a fibroadenoma with a significant calcification. Evolving lesions may also have a mixed pattern of posterior characteristics. A post-lumpectomy seroma that improves posteriorly is one such instance. Spiculation of the borders and posterior acoustic shadowing are two characteristics of fibrosis that show up as scarring and resorption of the fluid occur.

Figure 32

Combined Pattern

C. CALCIFICATIONS

When compared to mammography, calcifications have been less well described in the USG; however, they can be identified as echogenic foci, especially when they are part of a mass. Nowadays, intraductal calcifications can be well-depicted by high-frequency, high-resolution

transducers, primarily if they are superficial. With USG guidance, groups of microcalcifications located in fibroglandular tissue can be identified and biopsied. It should be noted that calcifications that are clearly benign may not always need to be mentioned. This is particularly true if the interpreting physician is worried that, should the calcifications be described in the report, the patient or referring clinician might conclude something other than complete benignity. The microcalcifications found in mammography may be viewed as echogenic specks that do not create shadowing and are occasionally difficult to differentiate from noise. However, they do not occupy enough of the acoustic beam to attenuate it. Large and microcalcification aggregates have the potential to weaken the acoustic beam and create shadowing.

1. Calcifications In A Mass

Calcifications embedded in a mass may show up nicely on USG, but they won't be as easy to see morphologically as they would on mammography. In a hypoechoic mass, these tiny hyperechoic foci will be easier to see than in a fibroglandular tissue volume. Mammographic microcalcifications won't weaken the USG beam unless they are tightly packed together or individually coarse.

Figure 33

Calcifications In A Mass

2. Calcifications Outside Of A Mass

Calcifications of fat or fibroglandular tissue are less noticeable at USG than when they are contained within a mass. Sometimes, small echogenic specks collected in tissue can be distinguished from acoustic speckles, transversely sectioned Cooper ligaments, or pectoral muscle fascicles by their distinct patterns. Individual calcifications that are not coarse enough will not cast a shadow because they take up too little space in the acoustic beam.

Calcifications may appear to be grouped in the area of tissue being studied with USG if they are numerous enough to show a pattern.

Using a vacuum-assisted biopsy instrument, USG can offer imaging guidance for a percutaneous biopsy when tiny calcifications within or outside of a mass are visible enough to target. It is usually necessary to get specimen radiography to confirm that the desired calcifications have been sampled.

Figure 34

Calcifications Outside Of A Mass

3. Intraductal Calcifications

Figure 35

Intraductal Calcifications

D. ASSOCIATED FEATURES

The following are some effects of a mass on its surroundings: aberrations of ductal patterns, straightening or thickening of Cooper ligaments, obliteration of the tissue planes by an infiltrating lesion, compression of the surrounding tissue, and an echogenic rim. These findings in the mammography lexicon are included in “architectural distortion.” There could be inflammatory cancer, radiation therapy, mastitis, or a systemic condition like congestive

heart failure causing the breast edema and skin thickening. Tissue stiffness characteristics and Doppler vascular findings of abnormalities in color and power are also related factors.

1. Architectural Distortion.

2. Duct Changes

Normally, ducts arborize smoothly, regularly, and gradually, getting progressively thinner in diameter as they move from the base of the nipple more into the parenchyma. Abnormal duct modifications can be identified by the presence of an intraductal mass, thrombus, or detritus, duct(s) extending to or from a malignant tumor, or cystic dilatation of a duct or ducts with irregularities in diameter and/or arborization.

3. Skin Changes

a. Skin Thickening

Skin thickening is described as being more than 2 mm and can be focal or widespread. However, normal skin thickness can reach up to 4 mm in the inframammary folds and periareolar area.

b. Skin Retraction

The skin surface is concave or ill-defined and appears pulled in.

4. Edema

Increased surrounding tissue echogenicity and reticulation—an angular network of hypoechoic lines that could be interstitial fluid or dilated lymphatics—are signs of edema. Significant skin thickening and edema are frequently found in conjunction with mastitis, systemic conditions such as congestive heart failure, and inflammatory breast cancer.

5. Vascularity

It is necessary to compare a tumor or other lesion to an unaffected or contralateral normal area of the same breast in order to determine whether it is hypovascular or hypervascular. There isn't a single vascular pattern associated with a certain condition. Technical considerations have a significant impact on both power and color Doppler, thus it's critical to avoid using vascularity as the sole diagnostic characteristic when interpreting results. Certain benign lesions, such as papillomas and inflammatory processes, may be extremely vascular, yet malignant lesions may not be.

a. Absent

Cysts are the most common avascular lesions. Some solid masses also have little or no vascularity. However, technical factors such as sensitivity settings for color Doppler (pulse repetition frequency should be set for low flow) may suppress the display of vascularity, falsely making a lesion appear avascular. Additionally,

vigorous compression may occlude small vessels; so when scanning with color or power Doppler, little or no pressure should be applied.

b. Internal Vascularity

Blood vessels are present within the mass. Vessels may penetrate the margin of the mass, or display an orderly or disorderly pattern within the mass. Abnormal flow patterns also may be found in breast tissue without the presence of a mass.

c. Vessels in Rim

The blood vessels may be marginal, forming part or all of a rim around a mass.

6. Elasticity Assessment

It is possible to take into account stiffness as a trait of masses and surrounding tissue in addition to their far more significant morphologic properties. This characteristic can be produced by applying human strain to the mass or by introducing ultrasonic energy into a mass, also known as a "shear wave." Benign lesions are supposed to be softer than cancers and the surrounding tissue, yet there is overlap with these expectations, much like with all other sonographic criteria. Current research is focused on determining the predictive value of different measurements of tissue stiffness, using both strain and shear-wave elastographic methods. To assist avoid misunderstandings, the color scale needs to be standardized. The descriptors SOFT, INTERMEDIATE, and HARD are relevant to all approaches and all systems.

The ultrasonic criteria of form, margin, and echogenicity are considerably more predictive of malignancy than hardness or softness. Therefore, for patient management, elastography examination should not take precedence over the more predictive morphologic markers of malignancy. Since many contemporary US units have elastography as a feature, it has been added to the lexicon. It is crucial to define and give names to the descriptors used in elasticity assessment. It is important to remember that inclusion does not imply support for the therapeutic validity of elasticity evaluation.

E. SPECIAL CASES

Cases classified as special have a distinct diagnostic or set of findings.

1. Simple Cyst

Four characteristics define a simple cyst: it is anechoic, round or oval, confined, and has posterior enhancement. When all four characteristics are present, the diagnosis of simple cyst—a typically benign finding—is established.

2. Clustered Microcysts

The lesion is comprised of a collection of anechoic masses, each measuring less than 2-3 mm, with thin septations (less than 0.5 mm) separating them and no distinct solid component. Although individual little cysts may cause microlobulation on the margins, the margin shouldn't be hazy. Diagnoses related to tissue that are connected to clustered microcysts include apocrine metaplasia and fibrocystic transformation.

3. Complicated Cyst

These are debris-filled cysts that frequently appear as uniform, low-level echoes, lack a distinct solid component, and have an invisible wall. These echoes may seem layered during real-time scanning and may gradually alter as the patient's position does. Echogenic foci that seem to scintillate as they move in a complex cyst are another possibility.

4. Mass in or on skin

These benign masses, which include neurofibromas, sebaceous or epidermal inclusion cysts, keloids, moles, pimples, and accessory nipples, are typically visible clinically. It is uncommon for a skin mass to be discovered to be a metastasis, especially when there is a scar from a mastectomy. In these cases, clinical data regarding the original tumor should be accessible to help with imaging interpretation. It is critical to identify the boundary between the skin and parenchyma and to confirm that the mass is, at minimum, largely contained within the two narrow bands of skin that reflect sound waves.

5. Foreign Body Including Implants

Marker clips, coils, cables, catheter sleeves, silicone that has been injected or leaked, glass or metal that has been damaged, and implants are examples of foreign bodies. When determining the existence and type of foreign materials inside the patient, the patient's history is typically helpful. The parenchyma's silicone has a recognizable "snowstorm" appearance at the US; it is represented as echogenic noise that spreads posterior to the mass and hides deep structures. Silicone bleed or infused silicone can pass through lymphatics and become lodged in lymph nodes, which subsequently display like symptoms.

6. Lymph Nodes — Intramammary

These are confined, oval lumps that include hilar fat and are frequently reniform. Although lymph nodes are found all over the breast, they are more frequently observed in the upper outer quadrant, particularly in the axillary tail, as they tend to enlarge the closer they are to the axilla. Typically, normal intramammary lymph nodes range in size from 3 to 4 mm to approximately 1 cm. Lymph nodes, whether found in the axilla or breast, are easily identifiable due to their echogenic fatty hilus and hypoechoic cortex. When the result shows distinctive benign characteristics of an intramammary lymph node, it may be deemed such.

7. Lymph Nodes — Axillary

Comment, clinical correlation, and further assessment may be necessary for enlarged axillary lymph nodes, particularly if they are new or noticeably rounder or larger than on a prior

exam. A typical axillary lymph node may have hyperechoic fatty hilar regions and measure up to 2 cm in length, while there is no standard measurement. When a significant collection of hilar fat is visible surrounding a relatively narrow cortical rim, lymph nodes greater than 2 cm may be typical.

The existence of metastasis is indicated by the representation of a cortical bulge or cortical area with altered echogenicity, but a lymph node lacking a fatty hilum or having a compressed fatty hilum may be abnormal. But no one sonographic characteristic may consistently differentiate a benign reactive node from a nodal malignancy. Individual differences exist in the quantity and size of axillary lymph nodes, so evaluating side-to-side symmetry may be beneficial.

8. Vascular Abnormalities

a. AVMs (Arteriovenous Malformations/Pseudoaneurysms)

b. Mondor Disease

9. Postsurgical Fluid Collection

Fluid collections, particularly postoperative seroma, are the only generally benign findings on postsurgical sonography (completely cystic, but occasionally also containing residual blood products that are mobile on real-time examination). Surrounding worrisome sonographic signs, like posterior shadowing, hypoechogenicity, an uneven and sometimes spiculated lateral edge, and architectural distortion, are typically present in the majority of other postsurgical abnormalities, especially those involving scar tissue.

10. Fat Necrosis

METHODOLOGY

This work was a prospective study done over two years at Shri B.M Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre from September 2022 to May 2024. One hundred women attending the OPD who fulfilled the necessary criteria were selected, and we acquired informed written permission after being advised about the project. We took a comprehensive history and isolated the issue with an SMG evaluation. We followed up with patients and obtained the corresponding histopathological results from the Department of Pathology.

INCLUSION CRITERIA: -

The study included female patients above 15 years of age who presented with breast masses and those willing for follow-up.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA: -

Female patients with breast masses who have: -

1. not attained menarche and,
2. those with recurrent lesions.

PROCEDURE:

We scanned the patients using GE VOLUSON S8 BT18 and GE VERSANA PREMIER machines.

The ipsilateral arm was abducted, the patient was positioned in a contralateral posterior oblique position, and the hand was placed beneath the head to flatten and thin the breast. The degree of posterior obliquity was varied to thin and flatten the portion of the breast undergoing sonographic evaluation. If a breast mass could only be felt when the patient is upright, then we occasionally performed US examination when the patient was seated. A 9 MHz linear transducer was employed. We adjusted the depth of the initial US survey of the breast region of interest to allow visualization of the pectoralis muscle at the posterior edge of the field of view. We changed the initial gain settings to depict fat as a mid-level gray at all levels. During real-time scanning, time gain compensation was changed either manually or automatically based on convenience. We considered the background tissue surrounding the lesion to help with precise lesion correlation across several modalities. Similarly, while scanning a palpable abnormality, we paid special attention to the area of clinical concern to guarantee that we scanned the correct location. We touched the palpable anomaly with a finger, and the transducer was positioned immediately over the area. We changed the depth or field of view as necessary once we discovered a lesion or when looking we were looking for a subtle finding. When a mass was identified and the US settings are optimized, US "sweeps" were used to scan the lesion in numerous planes across its whole length. Pictures of the lesion were taken from both the radial and antiradial viewpoints, and they were labeled with the centimeters away from the nipple as well as the "right" or "left" clock face position. Both with and without calipers, photos were taken to enable margin assessment on still images. Three dimensions should be used to evaluate lesion size: the longest horizontal diameter

should be reported first, then the anteroposterior diameter, and finally the orthogonal horizontal.

Figure 35

Position of Examination

Complementary Color and Power Doppler was performed to improve sensitivity in detecting malignant breast lesions. Sufficient care was taken to eliminate artefacts.

By comparing a lesion's strain to that of the surrounding normal tissue, strain ratios were calculated, and strain elastography was done. Elastography and B-mode US characteristics were carefully correlated.

The social sciences statistical program (Version 25) was used to do statistical analysis after the obtained data was entered into an Excel sheet from Microsoft. Tables, graphs, percentages, and diagrams were produced using the data distribution. Lastly, the relationship between the histological diagnosis and the SMG was examined using a Chi-square test. A cutoff point of $p < 0.05$ was used for significance.

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

A total of 100 patients were included in the study who fulfilled all the necessary criteria. A few of them presented with multiple masses with the total number of masses amounting to 118.

TABLE 3: Age wise distribution of patients and masses

Age	No. of Patients	No. of Masses	Percentage
< 20	5	5	4.2
20 - 29	24	32	27.1
30 - 39	25	27	22.9
40 - 49	15	21	17.8
50 - 59	14	14	11.9
60 - 69	11	11	9.3
70+	6	8	6.8

Graph 1: Age wise distribution of patients and masses

Table 4: Laterality of Symptoms

Laterality	No. of Patients	Percentage
Bilateral	7	7
Left Sided Only	43	43
Right Sided Only	50	50
Total	100	100.0

Graph 2: Laterality of Symptoms

Table 5: Distribution of Breast Composition

Composition	No. of Patients	Percentage
Heterogenous	42	42
Homogenous - fat	24	24
Homogenous - fibroglandular	34	34

Graph 3: Distribution of Breast Composition

Table 6: Location of Masses

Location (o'clock)	No. of Masses
1	6
2	5
3	19
4	10
5	5
6	11
7	7
8	4
9	18
10	5
11	5
12	8
All quadrants	5
Retroareolar	10

Graph 4: Location of Masses

Table 7: Distribution of masses by ACR US - BIRADS

BIRADS	No. of Masses	Percentage
2	53	44.9
3	10	8.5
4a	18	15.3
4b	7	5.9
4c	3	2.5
5	25	21.2
6	2	1.7

Graph 5: Distribution of masses by ACR US - BIRADS

Table 8: Distribution of USG Diagnoses

SMG Diagnosis	No. of Masses	Percentage
Breast Abscess	7	5.9
Breast Carcinoma	21	17.8
Breast Carcinoma with Bilateral Axillary Nodal Metastasis	1	.8
Breast Carcinoma with Ipsilateral Axillary Nodal Metastasis	10	8.5
Complex Breast Cyst	5	4.2
Fibroadenoma	46	39.0
Fibrocystic Change	10	8.5
Galactocele	2	1.7
Lipoma	4	3.4
Malignant Etiology	2	1.7
Phyllodes	3	2.5
Sebaceous Cyst	2	1.6
Simple Breast Cyst	5	4.2

Graph 6: Distribution of USG Diagnoses

Table 9: Distribution of HPR Diagnoses

HPR Diagnosis	No. of Masses	Percentage
Borderline Phyllodes	1	.8
Breast Abscess	6	5.1
Ductal Carcinoma In Situ	2	1.7
Encapsulated Papillary Carcinoma	1	.8
Epidermal Cyst	2	1.7
Fat Necrosis	2	1.7
Fibroadenoma	42	35.6
Fibroadenoma with Non - Proliferative Fibrocystic Change	1	.8
Fibrocystic Change with Periductal Mastitis	1	.8
Galactocele	2	1.7
Granulomatous Mastitis	2	1.7
Intraductal Papilloma	1	.8
Invasive Breast Carcinoma of No Special Type	26	22.0
Invasive Lobular Carcinoma	2	1.7
Lactating Adenoma	1	.8
Lipoma	5	4.2
Low Grade Fibromyxoid Sarcoma	1	.8
Mucinous Breast Carcinoma Type A	2	1.7
Mucinous Breast Carcinoma Type B	1	.8
Neuroendocrine Carcinoma	1	.8
Non - Proliferative Fibrocystic Change	10	8.5
Sclerosing Adenosis	1	.8
Simple Breast Cyst	5	4.2

Graph 7: Distribution of HPR Diagnoses

Table 10: Age with HPR Findings – Correlation

Age	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
< 20	5	0	5
(%)	6.1%	0.0%	4.2%
20 - 29	30	2	32
(%)	36.6%	5.5%	27.1%
30 - 39	26	1	27
(%)	31.7%	2.8%	22.9%
40 - 49	15	6	21
(%)	18.3%	16.7%	17.8%
50 - 59	5	9	14
(%)	6.1%	25%	11.9%
60 - 69	1	10	11
(%)	1.2%	27.8%	9.3%
70+	0	8	8
(%)	0.0%	22.2%	6.8%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

P value = 0.000 (<0.005)*

Graph 8: Age with HPR Findings – Correlation

Table 11: Duration of Symptoms with HPR Findings - Correlation

	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
< 12.00	72	7	79
(%)	87.8%	19.4%	66.9%
12.00 - 23.99	6	10	16
(%)	7.3%	27.8%	13.6%
24.00 - 35.99	2	8	10
(%)	2.4%	22.2%	8.5%
36.00 - 47.99	1	6	7
(%)	1.2%	16.7%	5.9%
48.00 - 59.99	1	4	5
(%)	1.2%	11.1%	4.2%
60.00+	0	1	1
(%)	0.0%	2.8%	0.8%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
P value = 0.000 (<0.005)*			

Graph 9: Duration of Symptoms with HPR Findings - Correlation

Table 12: Shape with HPR Findings - Correlation

	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
Irregular	10	31	41
(%)	12.2%	86.1%	34.7%
Oval	62	1	63
(%)	75.6%	2.8%	53.4%
Round	10	4	14
(%)	12.2%	11.1%	11.9%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
P value = 0.000 (<0.005)*			

Graph 10: Shape with HPR Findings - Correlation

Table 13: Margin with HPR Findings - Correlation

	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
Circumscribed	69	6	75
(%)	84.1%	16.7%	63.6%
Indistinct	12	6	18
(%)	14.6%	16.7%	15.3%
Microlobulated	0	7	7
(%)	0.0%	19.4%	5.9%
Spiculated	1	9	10
(%)	1.2%	25.0%	8.5%
Angular	0	8	8
(%)	0.0%	22.2%	6.8%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

P value = 0.000 (<0.005)*

Graph 11: Margin with HPR Findings - Correlation

Table 14: Orientation with HPR Findings - Correlation

	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
Not parallel	6	27	33
(%)	7.3%	75.0%	28.0%
Parallel	76	9	85
(%)	92.7%	25.0%	72.0%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
P value = 0.000 (<0.005)*			

Graph 12: Orientation with HPR Findings - Correlation

Table 15: Posterior Acoustic Features with HPR Findings - Correlation

	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
Combined	9	1	10
(%)	11.0%	2.8%	8.5%
Enhancement	30	9	39
(%)	36.6%	25.0%	33.1%
None	40	11	51
(%)	48.8%	30.6%	43.2%
Shadowing	3	15	18
(%)	3.7%	41.7%	15.3%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

P value = 0.000 (<0.005)*

Graph 13: Posterior Acoustic Features with HPR Findings - Correlation

Table 16: Calcifications with HPR Findings - Correlation

	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
In mass	11	14	25
(%)	13.4%	38.9%	21.2%
Intraductal	0	2	2
(%)	0.0%	5.6%	1.7%
None	70	20	90
(%)	85.4%	55.6%	76.3%
Outside Mass	1	0	1
(%)	1.2%	0.0%	0.8%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

P value = 0.001 (<0.005)*

Graph 14: Calcifications with HPR Findings - Correlation

Table 17: Vascularity with HPR Findings - Correlation

	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
Absent	65	2	67
(%)	79.3%	5.6%	56.8%
Internal Vascularity	11	34	45
(%)	13.4%	94.4%	38.1%
Vessels in Rim	6	0	6
(%)	7.3%	0.0%	5.1%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
P value = 0.000 (<0.005)*			

Graph 15: Vascularity with HPR Findings - Correlation

Table 18: Elasticity with HPR Findings - Correlation

	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
Hard	2	24	26
(%)	2.4%	66.7%	22.0%
Intermediate	7	11	18
(%)	8.5%	30.6%	15.3%
Soft	73	1	74
(%)	89.0%	2.8%	62.7%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
P value = 0.000 (<0.005)*			

Graph 16: Elasticity with HPR Findings - Correlation

Table 19: Lymph Nodal Involvement with HPR Findings - Correlation

Region	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
Axillary	7	16	23
(%)	8.5%	44.4%	19.5%
None	75	20	95
(%)	91.5%	55.6%	80.5%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

P value = 0.000 (<0.005)*

Graph 17: Lymph Nodal Involvement with HPR Findings - Correlation

Table 20: SMG findings with HPR findings - Correlation

SMG Findings	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
Benign (SMG)	80	0	80
(%)	97.6	0.0	67.8%
Malignant (SMG)	2	36	38
(%)	2.4	100	32.2%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
P value = 0.000 (<0.005)*			

Graph 18: SMG findings with HPR findings - Correlation

Table 21: SMG findings with HPR findings - Interpretation

Statistic	Benign	95% CI	Malignant	95% CI
Sensitivity	97.56%	91.47% to 99.70%	100.00%	90.26% to 100.00%
Specificity	100.00%	90.26% to 100.00%	97.56%	91.47% to 99.70%
PPV	100.00%	95.49% to 100.00%	94.74%	82.08% to 98.61%
NPV	94.74%	82.08% to 98.61%	100.00%	95.49% to 100.00%
Accuracy	98.31%	94.01% to 99.79%	98.31%	94.01% to 99.79%

Table 22: ACR US - BIRADS with HPR findings - Correlation

BIRADS	Benign (HPR)	Malignant (HPR)	Total
BIRADS 2	53	0	53
(%)	64.6%	0.0%	44.9%
BIRADS 3	10	0	10
(%)	12.2%	0.0%	8.5%
BIRADS 4a	16	2	18
(%)	19.5%	5.6%	15.3%
BIRADS 4b	2	5	7
(%)	2.4%	13.9%	5.9%
BIRADS 4c	0	3	3
(%)	0.0%	8.3%	2.5%
BIRADS 5	1	24	25
(%)	1.2%	66.7%	21.2%
BIRADS 6	0	2	2
(%)	0.0%	5.6%	1.7%
Total	82	36	118
(%)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

P value = 0.000 (<0.005)*

Graph 19: ACR US - BIRADS with HPR findings - Correlation

Table 23: Benign SMG findings with HPR findings – Correlation

SMG	Fibroadenoma (HPR)	Fibrocystic Disease (HPR)	Galactocele (HPR)	Lipoma (HPR)	Sebaceous Cyst (HPR)	SBC (HPR)
Fibroadenoma	42	2	0	1	0	0
Fibrocystic Disease	2	10	0	0	0	0
Galactocele	0	0	2	0	0	0
Lipoma	1	0	0	4	0	0
Sebaceous Cyst	0	0	0	0	2	0
Simple Breast Cyst	0	0	0	0	0	5

Table 24: Benign SMG findings with HPR findings - Interpretation

Statistic	Fibroadenoma	Fibrocystic Disease	Galactocele	Lipoma	Sebaceous Cyst	SBC
Sensitivity	97.67%	83.33%	100.00%	80.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Specificity	96.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
PPV	93.33%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
NPV	98.63%	98.15%	100.00%	99.12%	100.00%	100.00%
Accuracy	96.61%	98.31%	100.00%	99.15%	100.00%	100.00%

Graph 20: Benign SMG findings with HPR findings - Interpretation

Table 25: Suspicious SMG findings with HPR findings – Correlation

SMG	Breast Abscess (HPR)	Granulomatous Mastitis (HPR)	Phyllodes (HPR)	Fat Necrosis (HPR)	Malignancies (HPR)
Breast Abscess	6	1	0	0	0
Granulomatous Mastitis	0	0	0	0	0
Fat Necrosis	0	0	0	0	0
Phyllodes	0	0	1	0	1
Malignancies	0	1	0	1	36

Table 26: Suspicious SMG findings with HPR findings – Interpretation

Statistic	Breast Abscess	Malignancies
Sensitivity	100.00%	100.00%
Specificity	99.11%	97.56%
PPV	85.71%	94.74%
NPV	100.00%	100.00%
Accuracy	99.15%	98.31%

Graph 21: Suspicious SMG findings with HPR findings – Interpretation

DISCUSSION

For Indian women, breast cancer is a quickly becoming health concern. The general public's increased knowledge of its existence and treatment has led to a decline in death rates. Every woman is susceptible to breast cancer; however, the risk is higher for those over 50. Early identification of breast cancer is crucial for lowering its death toll. Age and single status are common factors affecting a patient's diagnosis delay.^{64,65}

Two low-cost methods for detecting breast cancer are clinical breast examination and breast self-examination. Mammography and ultrasound are two of the most effective imaging procedures for the diagnosis of breast cancer.

Breast lumps are thought to be the most common indicator of cancer. As a result, a significant number of patients who visit tertiary care institutions report having breast lumps.⁶⁶ Similar to our findings, other studies have also noted that breast lumps are a common complaint among patients visiting breast clinics.^{67,68} It has been suggested that being aware of a family history of breast cancer makes identifying breast tumors simpler.⁶⁹ The majority of patients in our study, however, had a poor familial history of breast cancer. Yamakanamardi S et al. performed a study with a similar demographic of patients.⁷⁰

It is recommended that women exhibiting symptoms such as a palpable breast lump, bloody discharge from the nipples, and skin dimpling or retraction undergo sonomammography, MRI, and mammography to confirm the diagnosis. Mammograms cannot always identify breast lesions or other abnormalities; pregnant women, people who are not allowed to be exposed to X-rays, and people with larger breasts are not allowed to use the mammography procedure. Sonomammography is, therefore, a perfect and trustworthy technique for the early identification of breast cancer under such circumstances.⁷¹

In the present prospective study conducted in BLDEU, Vijayapura, for two years, patients with complaints of breast lump/mass were examined clinically and underwent modalities like ultrasonography and histopathology. Most patients presented with unilateral complaints, with 50% being affected on the right and 43% on the left. A relatively smaller percentage (7%) presented with bilateral complaints. The left 3 o'clock and the right 9 o'clock positions are where the majority of lesions were found. These locations correspond to the upper outer quadrant on each side, indicating that the upper outer quadrant is the most common location for the onset of masses in this study.

Histopathological results were obtained by tissue biopsy excluding all cell block samples, and the correlation revealed 36 patients diagnosed as malignant while 82 patients were non-malignant. The findings included 26 patients with Invasive Breast Carcinoma of No Special Type, two patients each with Invasive Lobular Carcinoma, Ductal Carcinoma in situ and Type A Mucinous Carcinoma and individual cases of Low-Grade Fibromyxoid Sarcoma, Encapsulated Papillary Carcinoma, Neuroendocrine Tumor and Type B Mucinous Carcinoma among 36 malignant masses in concordance with reported literature.⁷² Among the 82 benign cases, most patients (n = 42) had Fibroadenomas.

The ages of the patients ranged from 15 to 82 years. Most patients (n = 25) were within the age group of 31 - 40 years, followed by 24 patients between 21 - 29 years. Studies with a comparable age range (above 30 years) for the evaluation of sonomammography were reported by Devolli-Disha et al.⁷³

It was also observed that patients between 20 and 50 years of age were more likely to present with multiple masses. 74.4% of the benign masses were found in patients younger than 40, whereas 91.7% of the malignant masses were found in patients aged more than 40. This suggests a positive relationship between the occurrence of malignancy and the increasing age of the patient.

A similar relationship was noted between the duration of symptoms and malignancy. 79 (66.9%) masses had a symptomatic history for less than a year, and 72 (91.1%) were benign. 29 (80.6%) of the malignant masses had a history of persisting for over a year.

The American College of Radiology prescribed a standard lexicon called BIRADS to standardize the assessment and interpretation of breast lesions in sonomammography, mammography and MRI. An ascending score is given, indicating the level of suspicion of malignancy.⁷⁴ Each mass's shape, margin, orientation, echopattern, posterior acoustic features, calcifications, internal vascularity, elasticity on strain elastography, and any additional related findings were documented. Several associations were found which were aligning with the literature by Mendelson EB et al.⁶³

Shape

31 (86.1%) of the 36 malignant masses displayed an irregular shape, while most benign lesions displayed either oval or round shapes. This data suggests a positive relationship between irregular shapes and malignancy and round or oval shapes with benignity.

Margin

69 (84.1%) of the benign masses had a circumscribed margin, which suggests a strong correlation between them. Masses with indistinct margins turned out to be benign in 12 cases. 83.3% of the malignant masses showed a lack of such a circumscribed margin and instead displayed indistinct margins in 6 masses, microlobulated margins in 7, angular margins in 8, and spiculated margins in 9.

Orientation

76 (92.7%) of all benign masses showed a parallel orientation. This starkly contrasts malignant masses, 27 (75%) of which showed a lack of parallel orientation.

Posterior Acoustic Features

Most of the masses evaluated did not feature any prominent posterior acoustic features. However, shadowing was observed to be observed 15 (41.7%) of the malignant masses. This is notable when compared to shadowing in only 3 (3.7%) of the 82 benign masses.

Calcifications

90 (76.3%) masses showed no evidence of calcific foci in the mass, duct or outside the mass. 70 (77.8%) of the masses were benign, and only 20 (22.2%) were malignant. Of the 25 (21.2%) masses that showed calcifications within, 14 (56%) turned out to be malignant, and 11 (44%) were benign. Both cases showing intraductal calcifications were malignant.

Vascularity

The majority of the masses observed did not display any significant internal vascularity (61.9%), and all but 2 of these masses turned out to be benign. In contrast, it was observed

that a higher number of masses showing internal vascularity (38.1%) turned out to be malignant (75.5%). Further observation noted that 94.4% of all malignancies detected in the study showed internal vascularity. This data suggests a positive relationship between internal vascularity and malignancy.

McNicholas MM et al. demonstrated a significant overlap between benign and malignant lesions regarding presence and flow signal types on USG Doppler interrogation of breast masses. However, it was seen that malignant lesions were far more likely to show two or more discriminatory signal types.⁷⁵

Elasticity

The masses that were found to be hard on strain elastography were found to be malignant in all but 2 of the cases. It was additionally found that 66.7% and 30.6% of the malignant masses were found to be hard and intermediate, respectively. This data suggests a positive relationship between the softness of a mass and benignity.

A study done by Kumar A et al showed that the sensitivity of elastography rose from 75.5% to 95.8% in the process of separating benign from malignant lesions.⁷⁶

Lymph Node Involvement

Prominent lymph nodes were noted in 23 of the cases in the axillary region. 16 of the cases showed malignant deposits secondary to primary breast malignancy, while the other 7 were due to reactive lymphadenitis. The underlying etiology of enlargement of lymph nodes was accurately differentiated in all but one of the cases. The exception being a case of fat necrosis showing all the BIRADS characteristics suggestive of a tumor coupled with inappropriate and inadequate history due to the patient and patient attender's recall bias misleading the clinical thought process.

In line with the findings published by Mendelson MB et al.⁶³, the current work used sonomammography to identify additional parameters such as lesion boundaries, echo patterns and other associated findings such as architectural distortion, duct changes, skin changes (thickening or retraction) and edema to distinguish between benign and malignant masses.

Each of the 118 masses were assigned a score and the findings correlated with histopathology. 53 (64.6%) of the masses were classified as BIRADS 2, and 10 (12.2%) came under BIRADS 3. These lesions were strongly suggested to be benign, and none of these masses were malignant on HPR correlation.

18 (15.3%) masses were scored as BIRADS 4a, indicating a low suspicion of malignancy. 16 (19.5%) of these turned out to be benign, whereas 2 (5.6%) were malignant. 7 (5.9%) BIRADS 4b class masses were found, out of which 5 were malignant. A notable case among 4b masses was a case of fat necrosis masquerading as a tumor. All 3 (2.5%) BIRADS 4c turned out to be malignant.

A total of 25 (21.2%) masses were given a BIRADS 5 score. 24 of these were malignant, with the exception of a case of granulomatous mastitis mimicking breast cancer. In addition, 2 (1.7%) biopsy-proven cases of breast cancer were also investigated, which fulfilled all the SMG lexicographic criteria for malignancy and were classified as BI-RADS 6.

The statistical analysis of BIRADS correlation with HPR shows a substantially high degree of concordance of BIRADS categories for distinguishing malignant masses from benign ones.

Abdulla N et al. stated that subdivisions 4a, 4b, and 4c were poorly reproducible among radiologists, and there was a trend toward lower concordance for small masses and malignant lesions.⁷⁷

According to Heinig J. et al., the assessment categories outlined in BIRADS for ultrasound⁷⁸ provide at least as good a means of distinguishing between malignant and benign solid masses as mammography does.⁷⁹

In this investigation, the sensitivity of sonomammography in identifying benign breast lesions was 97.56%, whereas the sensitivity for malignant lesions was 100%. Overall sonomammography sensitivity and specificity were evaluated by Badu-Peprah et al. and found to be 100% and 80.4%, respectively, indicating that sonomammography is a more sensitive test than mammography.⁸⁰

Devolli-Disha et al. found that in younger, symptomatic women (less than 45 years old), sonomammography had greater sensitivity and specificity (72.6% and 88.5%).⁷³ Similarly, Stavros et al. have demonstrated high sonomammography sensitivity (99.8%) when compared to mammography in differentiating benign and malignant breast masses.⁸¹ A study by Beerappa et al. found no discernible differences between sonomammography and mammography in terms of sensitivity or specificity for evaluating breast lesions.; however, there was a substantial difference between the use of mammography alone and the combination of mammography and sonomammography.⁸²

The accuracy for various benign masses such as fibroadenomas (96.61%), fibrocystic disease and its variants (98.31%), galactocele (100%), lipoma (100%) and simple breast cysts (100%) was found to be relatively high making SMG a reliable investigation in diagnosing benign masses.

Stavros et al⁸¹ stated that some solid lesions can be properly classified as benign with sonography, enabling imaging follow-up rather than biopsy.

Similar high-accuracy statistics were noted for suspicious masses having a higher BIRADS score, such as breast abscesses (99.15%) and malignancies (98.31%).

Comparatively, sonomammography's sensitivity and specificity in this study were greater than Gonzaga's study's, which found that sonomammography's corresponding values were 57.1% and 62.8%, respectively.⁸⁵

After doing a thorough analysis of the literature, Scheel et al.⁸³ discovered that adjunctive US screening for women with thick breasts improves cancer diagnosis when compared to mammography screening alone.

This observation was further consolidated in a study by Health Quality Ontario, which showed data demonstrating that screening with adjunct ultrasonography in addition to mammography detects more cases of disease with better sensitivity than mammography alone.⁸⁴

A study done by Saarenmaa I et al⁸⁵ on 572 histologically and 5 cytologically proven cases of breast cancer, concluded that both the sensitivity of mammography and the sensitivity of Ultrasonography are independently correlated with the patient's age and breast density. Age has an opposite impact on sensitivity, but density has a similar impact on mammography and

USG. The impact of breast density was generally equal to the impact of density at the tumour location on the sensitivity of both mammography and USG.

Thomassin-Naggara I, Tardivon A, Chopier J. (2014)⁹ concluded that a good interpretation on imaging should respect the BI-RADS terminology's descriptive guidelines for accurate interpretation of images.

High-resolution ultrasound is superior to other methods in several situations, according to Gupta K et al. These situations include the direct visualisation of intraductal masses with microcalcifications for guided biopsy, the distinction between solid and cystic lesions, the characterization of simple and complex cysts, the screening of mammographically inaccessible areas, and different lymph node stations.⁸⁶

According to Berg WA et al., when it comes to invasive malignancy, US and MR imaging were more sensitive than mammography in nonfatty breasts; nevertheless, there was a risk of overestimating the area of the tumor with both MR imaging and US. The combination of MR imaging, clinical examination, and mammography proved to be more sensitive than any of the tests used alone or in combination.⁸⁶

The overall accuracy of sonomammography in identifying benign and malignant masses is established in the current study by comparing the results of histology and sonomammography. Therefore, it can be applied as a screening study for breast masses. However, adjunctive modalities like mammography, MR imaging and histopathological correlation are needed to characterize malignant masses.

Limitations

There are a few possible restrictions on the investigation. Firstly, our study's small sample size prevented us from characterizing the microcalcifications according to their appearance and distribution, such as cluster, popcorn, etc. Secondly, since the study was limited to one location, conclusions should be cautiously extrapolated.

Therefore, it is advised that larger-scale research be conducted in the future to overcome these challenges.

CONCLUSION

Most breast masses occur between 20 and 40 years of age. However, most malignant masses appear in patients older than 40. The lesions present as lumps in most cases with varying associated features. Most masses are unilateral, predominantly right-sided.

The breast composition is divided such that heterogenous echotexture is seen predominantly in the younger age group, and the homogenous – fibroglandular variety is seen more commonly with increasing age. The most common location of the masses is the upper outer quadrant on either side, with the 3 o'clock position on the left side being the most common in this study.

The incidence of malignancy increases with age and with delay in presentation following symptom onset.

Most benign masses present with oval/round shape, circumscribed margin, parallel orientation, none or posterior acoustic enhancement and soft consistency on strain elastography. SMG shows some use in characterizing benign masses.

Masses with BIRADS descriptors of irregular shape, angular/microlobulated/spiculated margins, not parallel orientation, shadowing, calcifications, internal vascularity and hard consistency on strain elastography are significantly more likely to be malignant.

Additional features such as architectural distortion, skin changes (thickening and retraction), duct changes, and edema further help differentiate benign and malignant masses.

Although SMG can reliably differentiate benign and malignant masses, complementary modalities such as MRI, mammography and histopathology are needed to characterize the malignant masses.

Axillary lymph nodes are the first group to be involved in inflammatory and metastatic pathologies of the breast. Nodal metastasis can be reliably differentiated from reactive lymphadenitis using SMG combined with adequate clinical history.

Good sensitivity and specificity are demonstrated by sonomammography in identifying all breast lesions. As such, it may be deemed a more appropriate method of inquiry than mammography. For individuals under 40 years of age, it can serve as the primary screening method for breast lumps. Breast lesions can be better understood and managed with the help of BI-RADS classification.

The diagnostic accuracy of SMG can be further improve by combining it with complementary imaging modalities. Multimodality approach is more sensitive than any single modality alone.

Unnecessary interventions can be avoided in unequivocally benign lesions on SMG.

SUMMARY

This hospital-based prospective study included 100 patients with symptoms affecting the breast who underwent sonomammographic imaging, followed by histopathological correlation.

The majority of the patients were in the range of 20-40 years, with the right breast being slightly more affected than the left.

Most patients presented within a year of symptom onset.

The masses most commonly occurred in the upper quadrant of either breasts.

Fibroadenoma was the most frequent mass found, followed by breast cancer.

SMG is beneficial in isolating the lesion's location, size, and degree of involvement with the surrounding structures.

ACR BI-RADS incorporated SMG had a sensitivity of 97.56% and 100% for benign and malignant masses respectively. Additionally, the sensitivities for benign lesions like fibroadenomas, fibrocystic changes, and various cysts were very high.

This study demonstrated that ACR BI-RADS is a handy tool for differentiating benign and malignant masses and the advantages of SMG evaluation over clinical evaluation of symptomatic patients for the diagnosis and management planning of breast masses.

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ANNEXURE I

**BLDEU'S SHRI B.M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE
HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA**

**COMPARISON OF THE DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF SONOMAMMOGRAPHY
AGAINST HISTOPATHOLOGY IN THE EVALUATION OF BREAST MASSES**

PROFORMA

1. Name:

2. Age/Sex

3. Hospital No.:

4. Relevant complaints & history:

5. Ultrasound Findings:

6. Radiological Diagnosis.

7. Histopathological Examination findings:

ANNEXURE II

CONSENT FORM

COMPARISON OF THE DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF SONOMAMMOGRAPHY WITH HISTOPATHOLOGY IN THE EVALUATION OF BREAST MASSES

GUIDE : **DR. SHIVANAND V. PATIL**

P.G. STUDENT : **DR. GUTTA GOUTHAM KRISHNA**

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed that the purpose of this study is to compare the diagnostic accuracy of sonomammography with histopathology in the evaluation of breast masses.

PROCEDURE:

I understand that I will be asked to provide a detailed history and undergo clinical, ultrasonographic and histopathological examination for the purpose of this study.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that there is minimal risk involved in the above study.

BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in this study will help to compare the diagnostic accuracy of sonomammography with histopathology in the evaluation of breast masses.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by the study will become a part of hospital record and will be subjected to confidentiality and privacy regulations of hospital. If the data is used for publications the identity of the patient will not be revealed.

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask for more information about the study at any time.

REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and I may refuse to participate or withdraw from study at any time.

INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand in the unlikely event of injury to me during the study I will get medical treatment but no further compensations. I will not hold the hospital and its staff responsible for any untoward incidence during the course of study.

Date:

Dr. Shivanand V. Patil (Guide)

Dr. Gutta Goutham Krishna (Investigator)

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT:

I/my ward confirm that Dr. Gutta Goutham Krishna has explained to me the purpose of this research, the study procedure that I will undergo and the possible discomforts and benefits that I may experience, in my own language.

I/my ward have been explained all the above in detail in my own language and I understand the same. Therefore, I agree to give my consent to participate as a subject in this project.

(Participant)

Date

(Witness to above signature)

ಒಪ್ಪಿಗೆ ಪತ್ರ

COMPARISON OF THE DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF SONOMAMMOGRAPHY WITH HISTOPATHOLOGY IN THE EVALUATION OF BREAST MASSES

ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಿ: ಡಾ. ಶಿವಾನಂದ ವಿ. ಪಾಟೀಲ್

ಸ್ನಾತಕೋತ್ತರ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿ: ಡಾ. ಗುಟ್ಟಾ ಗೌತಮ್ ಕೃಷ್ಣ

ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶ:

ಸ್ತನ ದ್ರವ್ಯರಾಶಿಯ ಮೌಲ್ಯಮಾಪನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸೊನೊಮಾಮೊಗ್ರಫಿಯ ರೋಗನಿರ್ಣಯದ ನಿಖರತೆಯನ್ನು ಹಿಸ್ಟೋಪ್ಯಾಥಾಲಜಿಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಹೋಲಿಸುವುದು ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಉದ್ದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ನನಗೆ ತಿಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ವಿಧಾನ:

ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಉದ್ದೇಶಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ವಿವರವಾದ ಇತಿಹಾಸವನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಕ್ಲಿನಿಕಲ್, ಅಲ್ಟ್ರಾಸೋನೋಗ್ರಾಫಿಕ್ ಮತ್ತು ಹಿಸ್ಟೋಪ್ಯಾಥಾಲಜಿಕಲ್ ಪರೀಕ್ಷೆಗೆ ಒಳಗಾಗಲು ನನ್ನನ್ನು ಕೇಳಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಅಪಾಯಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅನಾನುಕೂಲಗಳು:

ಮೇಲಿನ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವುದೇ ಅಪಾಯವನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳು:

ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಲ್ಲಿ ನನ್ನ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ಸ್ತನ ದ್ರವ್ಯರಾಶಿಯ ಮೌಲ್ಯಮಾಪನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸೊನೊಮಾಮೊಗ್ರಫಿಯ ರೋಗನಿರ್ಣಯದ ನಿಖರತೆಯನ್ನು ಹಿಸ್ಟೋಪ್ಯಾಥಾಲಜಿಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಹೋಲಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಗೌಪ್ಯತೆ:

ನನ್ನ ಗುರುತನ್ನು ಯಾವುದೇ ಮೂರನೇ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಅಥವಾ ಪ್ರಕಟಣೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸಲಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಮತ್ತು ವೈದ್ಯಕೀಯ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯು ಆಸ್ಪತ್ರೆಯ ದಾಖಲೆಗಳ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಾಗಿ ವಿನಂತಿ:

ನಾನು ಯಾವುದೇ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಕುರಿತು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಕೇಳಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ನಿರಾಕರಣೆ ಅಥವಾ ಹಿಂತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆ:

ನಾನು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಒಪ್ಪಿಗೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ ಮತ್ತು ನಾನು ಯಾವುದೇ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ನಿರಾಕರಿಸಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ

ಗಾಯದ ಹೇಳಿಕೆ:

ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ನನಗೆ ಗಾಯವಾದಾಗ, ನನಗೆ ವೈದ್ಯಕೀಯ ಚಿಕಿತ್ಸೆ ನೀಡಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಆದರೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ಪರಿಹಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ. ಅಂತಹ ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಾನು ಆಸ್ಪತ್ರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅದರ ಸಿಬ್ಬಂದಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುವುದಿಲ್ಲ.

ದಿನಾಂಕ:

ಡಾ. ಶಿವಾನಂದ ವಿ. ಪಾಟೀಲ್ (ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಿ)

ಡಾ. ಗುಟ್ಟಾ ಗೌತಮ್ ಕೃಷ್ಣ (ತನಿಖಾಧಿಕಾರಿ).

ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ವಿಷಯದ ಒಪ್ಪಿಗೆ ಹೇಳಿಕೆ:

ಈ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಭವನೀಯ ಅನಾನುಕೂಲಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಡಾ. ಗುಟ್ಟಾ ಗೌತಮ್ ಕೃಷ್ಣ ನನ್ನ ಸ್ವಂತ ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸುತ್ತೇನೆ.

ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ನಾನು ಈ ಯೋಜನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಷಯವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಸಮ್ಮತಿಸುತ್ತೇನೆ.

(ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವವರು)

ದಿನಾಂಕ

(ಮೇಲಿನ ಸಹಿಗೆ ಸಾಕ್ಷಿ)

ದಿನಾಂಕ

ANNEXURE III

MASTER CHART

Patient No.	Age	Patient ID	Chief Complaint	Duration of Symptoms (in yr)	History of Illness	Breast Composition	Location	Size (cm)	Shape	Margins	Orientation	Echotexture	Posterior acoustic shadowing	Calcification	Vascularity	Internal Node (mm)	Skin	Other Associated Features	Special Cases	BRAMS	Ecology	Specific Diagnosis	Neoplastic Potential	Final Diagnosis	Stage of Upt
Ashwari	20	2550	Right Breast Lump	4	No	Homogenous-fat	9 o'clock	2.2x1.5x1.1	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Ajapa	33	26362	Right Breast Lump	2	No	Homogenous-fat	9 o'clock	2.5x1.0x0.7	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Girjala	65	26566	Right Breast Lump	12	No	anagenous-heterogeneous	Retroareolar	1.9x1.8x0.9	Irregular	Microlobulated	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	terral fasciast	Axillary	Hard	traction Nipple Retr	Yes	5	Malignant	tumor with ipsilateral Axillary Node	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	Melanosis
Hanra	45	26070	Right Breast Lump	2	No	Homogenous-fat	12 o'clock	2.5x1.0x0.6	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Heterogeneous	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	3	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Laltee	59	26040	Right Breast Lump	24	Yes	anagenous-heterogeneous	9 o'clock	2.1x1.5x1.1	Irregular	Indistinct	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	Shadowing	In mass	terral fasciast	None	Hard	None	No	5	Malignant	Breast Carcinoma	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	None
Lalita	30	2494	Right Breast Lump	12	Yes	Heterogeneous	12 o'clock	4.5x1.8x1.5	Irregular	Spiculated	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	terral fasciast	None	Hard	None	No	4c	Malignant	Breast Carcinoma	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	None
Lambika	65	26368	Right Breast Lump	36	No	anagenous-heterogeneous	9 o'clock	3.6x1.4x1.6	Irregular	Indistinct	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	Shadowing	In mass	terral fasciast	None	Hard	traction Nipple Retr	No	6	Malignant	Breast Carcinoma	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	None
Pallavi	29	27007	Right Breast Lump	05	No	Homogenous-fat	Retroareolar	1.9x1.0x1.2	Irregular	Indistinct	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	Axillary	Soft	Edema	Yes	4a	Benign	Breast Abscess	Benign	Breast Abscess	sple lymphate
Rajeshwari	40	22257	Right Breast Lump	6	No	Heterogeneous	3 o'clock	1.5x1.1x1.1	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	lesed in rim	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Rajeshwari	40	22257	Left Breast Lump	6	No	Heterogeneous	7 o'clock	1x1.1x0.6	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Rajeshwari	40	22257	Left Breast Lump	6	No	Heterogeneous	7 o'clock	1x0.5x0.4	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Sanjini	42	26043	Right Breast Lump	8	Yes	anagenous-heterogeneous	2 o'clock	4x3.8x3.2	Irregular	Circumscribed	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Intermediate	None	No	4a	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Sanjini	42	26043	Left Breast Lump	8	Yes	anagenous-heterogeneous	Retroareolar	2.8x1.7x1.9	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	anops Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	Duct Changes	Yes	4b	Benign	Complex Breast Cyst	Benign	Intraductal Papilloma	None
Sania	50	26368	Left Breast Lump	3	No	anagenous-heterogeneous	3 o'clock	0.7x0.5x0.5	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Anechoic	Enhancement	Outside Mass	Absent	None	Soft	None	Yes	2	Benign	Simple Breast Cyst	Benign	Simple Breast Cyst	None
Savitri	38	25902	Left Breast Lump	35	No	Homogenous-fat	10 o'clock	3.5x1.2x1.2	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Lipoma	Benign	Lipoma	None
Savitri Devi	20	27620	Right Breast Lump	2	No	Heterogeneous	9 o'clock	0.8x0.6x0.5	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Isoechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Shantika	50	27496	Right Breast Lump	6	No	Heterogeneous	6 o'clock	4.8x4.4x4	Irregular	Indistinct	Not parallel	anops Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	terral fasciast	None	Hard	Nipple Retraction	No	5	Malignant	Breast Carcinoma	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	None
Shruti	29	26323	Right Breast Lump	2	No	Heterogeneous	Retroareolar	1.5x1.1x1.1	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Shruti	29	26323	Left Breast Lump	2	No	Heterogeneous	Retroareolar	1.8x1.0x0.4	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Vijaylaxmi	32	26394	Right Breast Lump	4	No	Heterogeneous	5 o'clock	1.7x1.7x1.2	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	Combined	In mass	Absent	None	Intermediate	None	No	4a	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Vijaylaxmi	32	26394	Right Breast Lump	4	No	Heterogeneous	6 o'clock	0.5x0.7x0.5	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	Anechoic	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	Yes	2	Benign	Simple Breast Cyst	Benign	Simple Breast Cyst	None
Vijaylaxmi	32	26394	Right Breast Lump	4	No	Heterogeneous	Retroareolar	0.4x0.9x0.5	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	Anechoic	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	Yes	2	Benign	Simple Breast Cyst	Benign	Simple Breast Cyst	None
Lambika	62	37051	Right Breast Mass	48	No	anagenous-heterogeneous	4 quadrants	10x9x5	Irregular	Indistinct	Not parallel	anops Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	terral fasciast	Axillary	Hard	traction Nipple Retr	Yes	5	Malignant	tumor with ipsilateral Axillary Node	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	Melanosis
Lambika	62	37051	Left Breast Lump	48	No	anagenous-heterogeneous	3 o'clock	0.4x0.3x0.3	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	anops Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	Absent	Axillary	Intermediate	None	Yes	4a	Malignant	Complex Breast Cyst	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	Melanosis
Lambika	62	37051	Left Breast Lump	48	No	anagenous-heterogeneous	4 o'clock	0.3x0.3x0.3	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	anops Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	Absent	Axillary	Intermediate	None	Yes	4a	Malignant	Complex Breast Cyst	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	Melanosis
Jayashree	29	26793	Left Breast Lump	6	Yes	Homogenous-fat	3 o'clock	0.2x0.2x0.3	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	Anechoic	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	Yes	2	Benign	Simple Breast Cyst	Benign	Simple Breast Cyst	None
Merali	21	34902	Left Breast Lump	6	Yes	Heterogeneous	3 o'clock	3.5x1.5x1.6	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Nesamma	45	36082	Right Breast Lump	24	Yes	anagenous-heterogeneous	9 o'clock	1.9x1.7x1.5	Irregular	Spiculated	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	terral fasciast	Axillary	Intermediate	None	Yes	5	Malignant	tumor with ipsilateral Axillary Node	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	Melanosis
Nagesa	72	36607	Right Breast Mass	36	No	anagenous-heterogeneous	4 o'clock	3.3x1.8x1.2	Irregular	Spiculated	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	Shadowing	In mass	terral fasciast	Axillary	Hard	None	Yes	5	Malignant	tumor with ipsilateral Axillary Node	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	Melanosis
Anandika	32	37023	Right Breast Lump	3	No	Heterogeneous	9 o'clock	5x1x1.7	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Darshana	16	33894	Right Breast Lump	2	No	Heterogeneous	6 o'clock	1.8x1.0x0.4	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	Combined	In mass	terral fasciast	None	Soft	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Gourami	75	37894	Left Breast Mass	12	No	anagenous-heterogeneous	7 o'clock	3.3x3.8x1.7	Irregular	Spiculated	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	Shadowing	In mass	terral fasciast	Axillary	Hard	None	Yes	5	Malignant	tumor with ipsilateral Axillary Node	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	Melanosis
Kambika	48	26394	Left Breast Lump	2	Yes	Homogenous-fat	12 o'clock	1.9x1.2x1.5	Irregular	Spiculated	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	terral fasciast	None	Intermediate	None	No	4c	Malignant	Malignant Ecology	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	None
Madhura	58	26557	Right Breast Lump	24	No	anagenous-heterogeneous	7 o'clock	2.1x1.9x1.5	Irregular	Circumscribed	Not parallel	anops Solid Cyst	Combined	None	terral fasciast	Axillary	Intermediate	None	No	5	Malignant	Breast Carcinoma	Malignant	Microinvasive Carcinoma Stage A	None
Pooja	15	38007	Right Breast Lump	1	Yes	Heterogeneous	9 o'clock	1.5x1.2x1.1	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	lesed in rim	None	Intermediate	None	No	2	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None
Rahimi	65	30081	Left Breast Lump	24	Yes	Heterogeneous	Retroareolar	1.8x1.6x1.4	Irregular	Angular	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	Shadowing	In mass	terral fasciast	None	Hard	None	No	5	Malignant	Breast Carcinoma	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	None
Randhika	65	34007	Left Breast Pain	0.5	No	anagenous-heterogeneous	Retroareolar	2.4x1.8x1.5	Irregular	Indistinct	Parallel	Hyperechoic	Enhancement	None	Absent	Axillary	Soft	Edema	Yes	4a	Benign	Breast Abscess	Benign	Gonorrhoeus Infection	sple lymphate
Revika	41	22320	Left Breast Lump	12	Yes	anagenous-heterogeneous	7 o'clock	3.2x1.5x1.2	Irregular	Angular	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	terral fasciast	Axillary	Hard	None	Yes	5	Malignant	Breast Carcinoma	Malignant	sple Breast Carcinoma of No Special	Melanosis
Jayashree	16	26793	Left Breast Lump	12	No	Heterogeneous	3 o'clock	1.8x1.2x1.3	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	lesed in rim	None	Soft	None	No	3	Benign	Fibroadenoma	Benign	Fibroadenoma	None

Makabi	34	3574	Left Breast Lump	2	No	Homogenous-fat	5 o'clock	1.6x1.1x1.1	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	Duct Changes	No	2	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Lactating Adenoma	None
Sakrabati	70	23192	Right Breast Mass	24	No	anaplastic-irregular	8 o'clock	4.1x2.8x1.5	Irregular	Spiculated	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	Stenosing	In mass	terminal vascular	None	Hard	None	No	5	Malignant	Best Carcinoma	Malignant	size Best Carcinoma of No Special	None
Yakawa	40	38362	Left Breast Lump	12	No	Homogenous-fat	10 o'clock	1.2x0.8x1.1	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	Combined	In mass	Absent	None	Intermediate	Duct Changes	No	4a	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Fibroadenoma	None
Afia	20	38363	Right Breast Lump	0.5	Yes	Homogenous	7 o'clock	0.9x0.5x1.1	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	terminal vascular	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Fibroadenoma	None
Renka	38	38325	Left Breast Lump	12	No	Homogenous-fat	9 o'clock	1.8x1.4x0.9	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	isochoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Lipoma	Beige	Lipoma	None
Shaha	51	17019	Left Breast Lump	9	Yes	anaplastic-irregular	2 o'clock	1.3x1.1x0.8	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	anplex Solid Cyst	Combined	In mass	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Sclerosus Cyst	Beige	Sclerosus Cyst	None
Soldani	25	38389	Right Breast Lump	0.5	No	Homogenous	12 o'clock	1.9x1.6x1.5	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Fibroadenoma	None
Sawabi	25	38383	Biased Breast Lumps	2	No	anaplastic-irregular	40 quadrants	1.4x1.1	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	anplex Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	Duct Changes	No	2	Beige	Fibrocystic Change	Beige	Non-Proliferative Fibrocystic Change	None
Sheker	26	38390	Right Breast Lump	4	No	Homogenous-fat	6 o'clock	2.4x1.9x1.1	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Fibroadenoma	None
Rahika	25	38399	Left Breast Lump	3	No	Homogenous	Retromamary	2.2x0.9x1.4	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	anplex Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	Duct Changes	No	2	Beige	Gastrocele	Beige	Gastrocele	None
Kavei	20	38398	Left Breast Lump	1	No	Homogenous	4 o'clock	2.4x1.9x1.3	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	anplex Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	Absent	Axillary	Soft	Edema	Yes	4a	Beige	Breast Abscess	Beige	Breast Abscess	size lymphatic
Malama	60	23845	Left Breast Mass	36	Yes	anaplastic-irregular	4 o'clock	4.1x2.9x2.2	Irregular	Angular	Not parallel	Hyperechoic	Stenosing	None	terminal vascular	None	Intermediate	Duct Changes	No	5	Malignant	Best Carcinoma	Malignant	Invasive Lobular Carcinoma	None
Aneesa	56	25940	Right Breast Lump	12	Yes	anaplastic-irregular	5 o'clock	2.1x2.4x1.7	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	terminal vascular	None	Intermediate	None	No	4b	Malignant	Best Carcinoma	Malignant	size Best Carcinoma of No Special	None
Ashini	21	27792	Left Breast Lump	3	Yes	Homogenous	2 o'clock	2.7x2.1x1.7	Irregular	Angular	Parallel	Hyperechoic	Stenosing	In mass	terminal vascular	None	Intermediate	Size Thickening	No	4c	Malignant	Best Carcinoma	Malignant	size Best Carcinoma of No Special	None
Ashini	21	27792	Right Breast Lump	3	Yes	Homogenous	3 o'clock	2.7x2.1x1.2	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Fibroadenoma	None
Ashini	21	27792	Right Breast Lump	3	Yes	Homogenous	3 o'clock	2.4x2.2x1.7	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Fibroadenoma	None
Ashini	21	27792	Right Breast Lump	3	Yes	Homogenous	12 o'clock	1.9x1.5x1.2	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Fibroadenoma	None
Ashini	21	27792	Right Breast Lump	3	Yes	Homogenous	7 o'clock	0.5x0.7x0.5	Irregular	Indistinct	Parallel	anplex Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	terminal vascular	None	Soft	None	Yes	4b	Malignant	Complex Breast Cyst	Malignant	Ductal Carcinoma in Situ	None
Sahiba	34	17804	Right Breast Lump	2	Yes	Homogenous	3 o'clock	1.2x1.5x1.1	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	anplex Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrocystic Change	Beige	Non-Proliferative Fibrocystic Change	None
Shireki	43	17541	Right Breast Lump	6	No	Homogenous	6 o'clock	7x2.3x1.3	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	Combined	In mass	Absent	None	Soft	Duct Changes	No	4a	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Fibroadenoma	None
Shireki	43	17541	Left Breast Lump	6	No	Homogenous	3 o'clock	1.8x1.6x1.4	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	size with Non-Proliferative Fibrocystic	None
Renka	26	17540	Left Breast Lump	2	No	Homogenous	40 quadrants	1.3x1.1x0.8	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrocystic Change	Beige	Sclerosus Fibrosis	None
Kavini	33	66625	Left Breast Mass	8	No	Homogenous	40 quadrants	2x0.6	Irregular	Indistinct	Not parallel	anplex Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	terminal vascular	None	Hard	axillary Dissection, Size 10	No	4a	Beige	Phyllodes	Beige	Spindle Cell Phyllodes	None
Sheker	26	17570	Right Breast Lump	5	No	Homogenous-fat	4 o'clock	1.7x1.5x0.9	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Non-Proliferative Fibrocystic Change	None
Begum Nida	30	25943	Left Breast Lump	3	No	Homogenous-fat	3 o'clock	7x1x1.3	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Homogenous	Stenosing	In mass	terminal vascular	None	Soft	None	No	4a	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Fibroadenoma	None
Ashabi	56	17611	Right Breast Lump	6	No	anaplastic-irregular	5 o'clock	2.4x2.2x1.2	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	Stenosing	In mass	terminal vascular	None	Intermediate	None	No	4b	Malignant	Best Carcinoma	Malignant	Ductal Carcinoma in Situ	None
Pankaj	23	17570	Left Breast Lump	2	Yes	Homogenous	4 o'clock	1.4x2x1.1	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	Vegetal in Rim	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Fibroadenoma	None
Gaeta	68	38346	Left Breast Lump	8	No	anaplastic-irregular	9 o'clock	3.2x2.5x1.3	Irregular	Microlobulated	Not parallel	Homogenous	Enhancement	None	terminal vascular	Axillary	Hard	axillary Dissection	Yes	5	Malignant	size with ipsilateral Axillary Node	Malignant	Neuroendocrine Carcinoma	Melanosis
Sahini	45	17082	Left Breast Lump	2	Yes	Homogenous-fat	2 o'clock	1.9x1.6x1.5	Irregular	Indistinct	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	terminal vascular	None	Soft	Duct Changes	No	4a	Beige	Fibrocystic Change	Beige	complex Change with Periductal Wall	None
Shireki	43	17089	Right Breast Lump	4	No	Homogenous	7 o'clock	1.6x1.2x1.1	Oval	Indistinct	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	terminal vascular	None	Soft	Duct Changes	No	3	Beige	Fibrocystic Change	Beige	Non-Proliferative Fibrocystic Change	None
Shireki	43	17089	Left Breast Lump	4	No	Homogenous	6 o'clock	1.2x1x0.7	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	None	None	terminal vascular	None	Soft	Duct Changes	No	3	Beige	Fibrocystic Change	Beige	Non-Proliferative Fibrocystic Change	None
Shireki	43	17089	Left Breast Lump	4	No	Homogenous	12 o'clock	0.8x0.5x0.6	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	anplex Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	Duct Changes	No	3	Beige	Fibrocystic Change	Beige	Non-Proliferative Fibrocystic Change	None
Bocoma	22	17045	Right Breast Lump	2	No	Homogenous	1 o'clock	2.1x0.9x1.1	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibroadenoma	Beige	Fibroadenoma	None
Sajja	43	17043	Right Breast Mass	12	No	Homogenous	40 quadrants	4.5x3.2x1.3	Irregular	Indistinct	Not parallel	Homogenous	None	None	terminal vascular	None	Hard	axillary Dissection, Duct	No	4b	Malignant	Phyllodes	Malignant	Low Grade Fibromyal Carcinoma	None
Akorda	25	38379	Left Breast Lump	5	Yes	Homogenous	3 o'clock	1.8x1.2x1.3	Oval	Circumscribed	Parallel	isochoic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Lipoma	Beige	Lipoma	None
Aranya	60	36664	Right Breast Mass	36	Yes	anaplastic-irregular	10 o'clock	3x2.3x2.1	Irregular	Angular	Not parallel	Homogenous	None	In mass	terminal vascular	Axillary	Hard	None	No	5	Malignant	Best Carcinoma	Malignant	size Best Carcinoma of No Special	None
Shweta	20	7776	Left Breast Lump	0.5	Yes	Homogenous	6 o'clock	7x1x1.3	Oval	Indistinct	Parallel	Hyperechoic	Enhancement	None	Absent	Axillary	Soft	Edema	Yes	3	Beige	Breast Abscess	Beige	Breast Abscess	size lymphatic
Shaha	54	1154	Right Breast Mass	18	No	anaplastic-irregular	8 o'clock	2.8x2.4x2.1	Irregular	Angular	Not parallel	anplex Solid Cyst	Enhancement	None	terminal vascular	None	Intermediate	None	No	5	Malignant	Best Carcinoma	Malignant	Mucous Breast Carcinoma Type 3	None
Lamini	45	38386	Right Breast Lump	0.5	Yes	anaplastic-irregular	5 o'clock	2.7x2.2x1.7	Irregular	Indistinct	Parallel	Homogenous	Enhancement	None	Absent	Axillary	Soft	Edema	Yes	4a	Beige	Sclerosus Cyst	Beige	Sclerosus Cyst	size lymphatic
Rongaj	62	38459	Left Breast Mass	36	No	anaplastic-irregular	6 o'clock	3.1x2.7x2.1	Round	Circumscribed	Parallel	Hyperechoic	Enhancement	In mass	terminal vascular	None	Intermediate	None	No	4b	Malignant	Malignant Etiology	Malignant	Encapsulated Proliferative Carcinoma	None

Mesoh	70	5005	Left Vest	Wax	14	No	mpexus-hinged	12" oval	29x29x7	Regular	Microbeaded	Not padded	mpexus SinoCyt	None	None	terral lacust	None	Hard	None	No	5	Walgent	Beez Caronna	Walgent	Micro Vest Caronna (No Special)	None
Amio	30	5073	Left Vest	Lump	3	Yes	Heterogeneous	4" oval	15x14x12	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	mpexus SinoCyt	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	Duct Charges	No	3	Beige	Fluoroptic Charge	Beige	Non-Polished-Fluoroptic Charge	None
Sarasome	33	5073	Right Vest	Lump	2	Yes	Homogenous-fat	12" oval	26x15x14	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Saleer	36	7350	Right Vest	Lump	6	No	Homogenous-fat	7" oval	24x15x7	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	Enhancement	None	terral lacust	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Stati	29	4657	Right Vest	Lump	2	No	Homogenous-fat	9" oval	14x13x13	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Heterogeneous	Enhancement	None	terral lacust	None	Soft	None	No	3	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Non-Polished-Fluoroptic Charge	None
Saipa	27	3020	Right Vest	Lump	4	No	Heterogeneous	12" oval	19x12x11	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	Combined	In mass	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Raepa	45	9864	Right Vest	Wax	5	No	mpexus-hinged	4" oval	24x2x15	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Heterogeneous	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Radii	75	5979	Left Vest	Wax	40	No	mpexus-hinged	3" oval	29x15x7	Regular	Microbeaded	Not padded	Heterogeneous	Stowing	In mass	terral lacust	None	Hard	Duct Charges	No	5	Walgent	Beez Caronna	Walgent	see Beez Caronna of No Special	None
Bevati	34	1099	Right Vest	Lump	24	No	Heterogeneous	6" oval	25x12x11	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Heterogeneous	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Lipona	None
Gangaji	65	9436	Left Vest	Wax	12	Yes	mpexus-hinged	5" oval	19x17x15	Regular	Spooled	Not padded	Heterogeneous	Stowing	None	terral lacust	None	Hard	Duct Charges	No	5	Walgent	Beez Caronna	Walgent	Incise Label Caronna	None
Shipa	37	5937	Right Vest	Lump	0.5	Yes	Heterogeneous	3" oval	23x15x7	Round	Indistinct	Not padded	Heterogeneous	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	Ebena, Duct Charges	No	4a	Beige	Beez Access	Beige	Beez Access	None
Shagapma	58	5020	Right Vest	Lump	40	No	mpexus-hinged	9" oval	17x12x11	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Lipona	Beige	Lipona	None
Wolpelen	45	11009	Right Vest	Lump	24	Yes	Homogenous-fat	10" oval	22x21x17	Regular	Microbeaded	Not padded	Hypertonic	Stowing	introduced	terral lacust	Aulay	Hard	Duct Charges	Yes	5	Walgent	none with updated Aulay Node	Walgent	see Beez Caronna of No Special	Mesozoic
Fairne	21	2904	Right Vest	Lump	3	Yes	Heterogeneous	12" oval	29x15x7	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	Combined	In mass	Absent	None	Soft	Duct Charges	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Fairne	21	2904	Right Vest	Lump	6	Yes	Heterogeneous	12" oval	21x15x12	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	Duct Charges	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Fairne	21	2904	Left Vest	Lump	6	Yes	Heterogeneous	12" oval	19x14x13	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Fairne	21	2904	Left Vest	Lump	6	Yes	Heterogeneous	12" oval	15x10x11	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Raipa	65	007004010	Right Vest	Wax	12	Yes	mpexus-hinged	2" oval	34x20x15	Regular	Agular	Not padded	mpexus SinoCyt	Enhancement	In mass	terral lacust	Aulay	Hard	in Thickening Mipel	Yes	5	Walgent	none with updated Aulay Node	Walgent	see Beez Caronna of No Special	Mesozoic
Shiana	30	5080	Left Vest	Lump	10	Yes	Heterogeneous	3" oval	35x24x18	Regular	Indistinct	Not padded	mpexus SinoCyt	Stowing	None	Absent	None	Hard	Duct Charges	No	5	Walgent	Beez Caronna	Beige	Growthcut Mesitic	None
Hareeba	17	10055	Left Vest	Lump	4	Yes	Homogenous-fat	4" oval	22x19x7	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Heterogeneous	None	In mass	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	3	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Ropahre	51	30162	Right Vest	Wax	24	Yes	Heterogeneous	10" oval	31x17x13	Regular	Spooled	Not padded	Heterogeneous	Stowing	introduced	terral lacust	Aulay	Hard	e-Release, Duct Cha	Yes	6	Walgent	none with updated Aulay Node	Walgent	see Beez Caronna of No Special	Mesozoic
Gaipi	10	31892	Left Vest	Lump	3	No	Heterogeneous	3" oval	21x10x11	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	lacustic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Kaiba	29	7090	Right Vest	Lump	2	No	Homogenous-fat	7" oval	19x15x11	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Heterogeneous	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Gastricite	Beige	Gastricite	None
Govi	16	73993	Left Vest	Lump	4	No	Heterogeneous	3" oval	25x10x19	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Megama	42	50493	Left Vest	Wax	60	Yes	Heterogeneous	7" oval	35x21x21	Regular	Agular	Not padded	Heterogeneous	Stowing	In mass	terral lacust	Aulay	Hard	in Thickening Mipel	Yes	5	Walgent	none with updated Aulay Node	Walgent	see Beez Caronna of No Special	Mesozoic
Sidana	37	30190	Left Vest	Lump	24	No	Homogenous-fat	9" oval	32x19x13	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	mpexus SinoCyt	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Intermediate	None	No	4a	Beige	Complex Vest Cyt	Beige	Fat Mesitic	None
Revika	33	10101	Right Vest	Lump	3	No	Heterogeneous	8" oval	28x21x12	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Heterogeneous	Combined	In mass	terral lacust	None	Soft	None	No	3	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Mika	23	10082	Left Vest	Lump	5	Yes	Heterogeneous	3" oval	21x15x12	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Susana	54	30200	Left Vest	Lump	0.5	No	mpexus-hinged	6" oval	29x24x13	Regular	Indistinct	Not padded	Hypertonic	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	No	4a	Beige	Beez Access	Beige	Beez Access	None
SwathDag	10	29304	Left Vest	Lump	12	No	Heterogeneous	5" oval	34x25x15	Regular	Indistinct	Not padded	Hypertonic	None	None	terral lacust	None	Intermediate	Duct Charges	No	4a	Beige	Phylotax	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Shreik	32	30192	Right Vest	Lump	6	No	Homogenous-fat	3" oval	23x21x11	Round	Cumulated	Padded	Aerobic	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	None	Yes	2	Beige	Simple Vest Cyt	Beige	Simple Vest Cyt	None
Shreip	21	33209	Right Vest	Lump	2	No	Heterogeneous	5" oval	16x10x14	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	Combined	In mass	Absent	Aulay	Soft	None	No	2	Beige	Fibrosoma	Beige	Fibrosoma	None
Karabala	35	20022	Right Vest	Wax	36	Yes	mpexus-hinged	8" oval	34x25x15	Regular	Microbeaded	Padded	Hypertonic	None	None	terral lacust	None	Hard	Thickening Duct Cha	No	5	Walgent	Beez Caronna	Walgent	see Beez Caronna of No Special	None
Sakhida	36	37702	Right Vest	Lump	15	Yes	mpexus-hinged	9" oval	21x14x13	Regular	Spooled	Padded	Heterogeneous	Stowing	None	Veget in film	Aulay	Intermediate	None	Yes	4b	Walgent	Beez Caronna	Beige	Fat Mesitic	Beige
Lamin	35	13592	Left Vest	Lump	6	No	Homogenous-fat	4" oval	13x16x19	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Hypertonic	None	None	Absent	None	Soft	Duct Charges	No	2	Beige	Fluoroptic Charge	Beige	Non-Polished-Fluoroptic Charge	None
Amika	35	30740	Left Vest	Lump	0.5	No	Homogenous-fat	Hexagonal	12x11x11	Oval	Indistinct	Padded	Heterogeneous	Enhancement	None	Absent	None	Soft	Ebena	No	4a	Beige	Beez Access	Beige	Beez Access	None
Bazama	52	4003	Right Vest	Lump	2	Yes	mpexus-hinged	5" oval	23x21x15	Regular	Spooled	Not padded	Heterogeneous	Stowing	In mass	terral lacust	None	Hard	None	No	5	Walgent	Beez Caronna	Walgent	see Beez Caronna of No Special	None
Aika	30	37023	Left Vest	Lump	2	Yes	Heterogeneous	9" oval	15x11x14	Oval	Cumulated	Padded	Heterogeneous	None	None	Veget in film	None	Soft	Duct Charges	No	2	Beige	Fluoroptic Charge	Beige	Non-Polished-Fluoroptic Charge	None
Idika	60	39142	Right Vest	Lump	24	No	mpexus-hinged	12" oval	17x13x15	Regular	Microbeaded	Not padded	Hypertonic	None	None	terral lacust	Aulay	Hard	thickening Mipel Base	Yes	5	Walgent	none with updated Aulay Node	Walgent	see Beez Caronna of No Special	Mesozoic

CASE REPORTS

Case 1: Fibroadenoma

A 40-year-old woman complained of a painless lump in her right breast that had been there for six months. A positive family history of breast cancer was present in the patient. Clinical examination revealed a painless mobile mass in the right breast's upper inner quadrant.

Figure 37

Case 1: Fibroadenoma

SMG revealed a heterogenous breast composition with an oval-shaped, circumscribed, heterogenous lesion in parallel orientation, showing no significant posterior acoustic features in the 1 o'clock position of the right breast measuring about 1.4 x 1.6 x 0.8 cm. Adjacent duct ectasia was noted. The lesion showed no significant vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and was graded as soft on strain elastography. There was no evidence of calcifications, architectural distortion, skin changes or edema.

A diagnosis of an ACR BIRADS 2 lesion with features favoring a Fibroadenoma was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Fibroadenoma.

Case 2: Fibroadenoma

A 32-year-old woman complained of a painless lump in her right breast that had been there for six months. The patient had a negative family history of breast cancer. Clinical examination revealed a painless mobile mass in the right breast's upper outer quadrant.

Figure 38

Case 2: Fibroadenoma

SMG revealed a heterogenous breast composition with an oval-shaped, circumscribed, hypoechoic lesion in parallel orientation, showing mild posterior acoustic enhancement in the 11 to 12 o'clock position measuring about 3.6 x 1.9 x 2.2 cm in the right breast. The lesion showed no significant vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and was graded as intermediate on strain elastography. There was no evidence of calcifications, architectural distortion, skin changes or edema.

A diagnosis of an ACR BIRADS 3 lesion with features favoring a Fibroadenoma was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Fibroadenoma.

Case 3: Galactocele

A 25-year-old lactating mother presented with complaints of a painless lump in the left breast for 2 months. The patient had a negative family history of breast cancer. Clinical examination revealed a painless mobile mass in the left breast's upper inner quadrant.

Figure 39

Case 3: Galactocele

SMG revealed a heterogenous breast composition with an oval-shaped, circumscribed, anechoic lesion in parallel orientation, showing posterior acoustic enhancement in the 10 o'clock position with multiple low level internal echoes and debris measuring about 1.6 x 1.8 x 1.3 cm. Adjacent duct ectasia was noted. The lesion showed no significant vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and was graded as soft on strain elastography. There was no evidence of calcifications, architectural distortion, skin changes or edema.

A diagnosis of an ACR BIRADS 2 lesion with features favoring a Galactocele was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Galactocele.

Case 4: Simple Breast Cyst

A 39-year-old female presented with complaints of a painless lump in the left breast for 6 months. A positive family history of breast cancer was present in the patient. Clinical examination revealed a painless mobile mass in the left breast's upper inner quadrant.

Figure 40

Case 4: Simple Breast Cyst

SMG revealed a heterogenous breast composition with an oval shaped, circumscribed, anechoic lesion in parallel orientation, showing posterior acoustic enhancement in the 12 o'clock position measuring about 1.3 x 2.7 x 3.4 cm. The lesion showed no significant vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and was graded as soft on strain elastography. There was no evidence of calcifications, architectural distortion, skin changes, duct changes or edema.

A diagnosis of an ACR BIRADS 2 lesion with features favoring a Simple Breast Cyst was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Simple Breast Cyst.

Case 5: Breast Abscess

A 20-year-old female presented with complaints of a painful lump in the left breast for 1 week. A positive family history of breast cancer was present in the patient. Clinical examination demonstrated a tender lump and a local rise in temperature.

Figure 41

Case 5: Breast Abscess

SMG revealed a heterogenous breast composition with an oval-shaped, indistinctly marginated, hypoechoic lesion in parallel orientation, showing posterior acoustic enhancement in the 6 o'clock position with significant perilesional edema measuring about 2.1 x 1.6 x 2 cm. The lesion showed no significant vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and was graded as soft on strain elastography. There was no evidence of calcifications, architectural distortion, skin changes or duct changes.

A diagnosis of an ACR BIRADS 4a lesion with features favoring a Breast Abscess was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Secondarily Infected Galactocele leading to Abscess formation.

Case 6: Fibrocystic Change

A 30-year-old female patient complained of multiple small painful lumps in the left breast for 2 months, with the pain showing cyclical variation. A positive family history of breast cancer was present in the patient. Clinical examination demonstrated multiple small tender lumps in multiple quadrants of the left breast.

Figure 42

Case 6: Fibrocystic Change

SMG revealed a heterogenous breast composition with a few oval-shaped, circumscribed, heterogenous lesions in parallel orientation, showing no significant posterior acoustic features with adjacent duct ectasia, the largest one measuring about 1.3 x 0.6 x 1 cm in the 9 o'clock position of the left breast. The lesions showed no significant vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and were graded as soft on strain elastography. There was no evidence of calcifications, architectural distortion, skin changes or edema.

A diagnosis of an ACR BIRADS 4a lesion with features favoring Fibrocystic Change was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Non – Proliferative Fibrocystic Change.

Case 7: Intraductal Papilloma

A 42-year-old female patient presented with complaints of a painless lump in the left breast for 8 months. A positive family history of breast cancer was present in the patient. Clinical examination revealed a painless immobile mass in the retroareolar position of the left breast.

Figure 43

Case 7: Intraductal Papilloma

SMG revealed a homogenous - fibroglandular breast composition with an oval-shaped, microlobulated, complex mixed solid cystic lesion in parallel orientation, showing posterior acoustic enhancement with adjacent duct ectasia measuring about 2.8 x 2.7 x 1.9 cm in the retroareolar position of the left breast. The lesion showed no significant vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and was graded as soft on strain elastography. There was no evidence of calcifications, architectural distortion, skin changes or edema.

A diagnosis of an ACR BIRADS 4b lesion with features favoring Complex Breast Cyst was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Intraductal Papilloma.

Case 8: Invasive Breast Carcinoma of No Special Type

A 75-year-old female patient presented with complaints of a large and painless mass in the left breast for 1 year. The patient had a negative family history of breast cancer. Clinical examination revealed a large painless immobile mass in the left breast's upper outer quadrant and a few prominent lymph nodes in the ipsilateral axillary region. The overlying skin appeared thickened with associated nipple retraction.

Figure 44

Case 8: Invasive Breast Carcinoma of No Special Type

SMG revealed a homogenous - fibroglandular breast composition with a large irregular-shaped, spiculated, hypoechoic lesion in a not parallel orientation, showing foci of calcifications within, posterior acoustic shadowing and architectural distortion measuring about 3.3 x 3.8 x 2.7 cm in the 1 to 4 o'clock position of the left breast. The lesion showed significant internal vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and were graded as hard on strain elastography. There was no evidence of duct changes or edema.

A diagnosis of an ACR BIRADS 5 lesion with features favoring Breast Carcinoma was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Invasive Breast Carcinoma of No Special Type.

Figure 45

Case 8: Nodal Metastasis

SMG also revealed a few enlarged lymph nodes with loss of fatty hilum were noted in the ipsilateral axillary region. The lesions showed no significant vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and were graded as hard on strain elastography.

A diagnosis of Ipsilateral Nodal Metastasis was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Malignant Nodal Deposits.

Case 9: Invasive Breast Carcinoma of No Special Type

A 65-year-old female patient complained of a painless mass in the left breast for 1 year. A positive family history of breast cancer was present in the patient. Clinical examination revealed a painless immobile mass in the left breast's lower outer quadrant.

Figure 46

Case 9: Invasive Breast Carcinoma of No Special Type

SMG revealed a homogenous - fibroglandular breast composition with a irregular-shaped, angularly margined, hypoechoic lesion in a not parallel orientation, showing posterior acoustic enhancement measuring about 1.5 x 1.2 x 1.5 cm in the 5 o'clock position of the left breast. The lesion showed internal significant vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and were graded as hard on strain elastography. There was no evidence of calcifications, skin changes, duct changes or edema.

A diagnosis of an ACR BIRADS 5 lesion with features favoring Breast Carcinoma was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Invasive Breast Carcinoma of No Special Type.

Case 10: Mucinous Breast Carcinoma Type B

A 54-year-old female patient had complaints of a large and painless mass in the right breast for 2 years. A positive family history of breast cancer was present in the patient. Clinical examination revealed a large painless immobile mass in the right breast's upper outer quadrant and a few prominent lymph nodes in the ipsilateral axillary region.

Figure 47

Case 10: Mucinous Breast Carcinoma Type B

SMG revealed a homogenous - fibroglandular breast composition with a large irregular-shaped, microlobulated, hypoechoic lesion in a not parallel orientation, showing posterior acoustic enhancement and architectural distortion measuring about 3.2 x 3 x 3.2 cm in the 8 to 10 o'clock position of the right breast. The lesion showed internal vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and were graded as intermediate on strain elastography. There was no evidence of skin changes, duct changes or edema.

A diagnosis of an ACR BIRADS 5 lesion with features favoring Breast Carcinoma was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Mucinous Breast Carcinoma Type B.

Figure 48

Case 10: Nodal Metastasis

SMG also revealed a few enlarged lymph nodes with cortical thickening in the ipsilateral axillary region. The lesions showed no significant vascularity on Color Doppler Interrogation and were graded as hard on strain elastography.

A diagnosis of Ipsilateral Nodal Metastasis was made.

Histopathology returned a positive result for Malignant Nodal Deposits.

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

BLDE

(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956

Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)

The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 757/2022-23

30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on **Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology** scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "COMPARISON OF THE DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF SONOMAMMOGRAPHY WITH HISTOPATHOLOGY IN THE EVALUATION OF BREAST MASSES".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: DR. GOUTHAM KRISHNA

**NAME OF THE GUIDE: DR. SHIVANAND PATIL & DR. VIJAYALAXMI PATIL (CO-GUIDE),
Dept. of Radiology.**

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA

**Chairman,
Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)**

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutiny

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Dr. Akram A. Nalkwadi
Member Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA

**MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura-586103, Karnataka**

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapura - 586103, Karnataka, India.

BLDE (DU): Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263303, Website: www.bldeu.ac.in, E-mail: office@bldeu.ac.in
College: Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263019, E-mail: bmprnc.principal@bldeu.ac.in